

SEYCHELLES NATIONAL SEAGRASS MONITORING PROTOCOLS

A Tiered Framework for Science, Conservation, Restoration and Citizen Science

SEYCHELLES CONSERVATION
AND CLIMATE ADAPTATION
TRUST

SeyCCAT

STANDARDISED SEAGRASS ASSESSMENT, MONITORING AND RESTORATION
PROTOCOLS FOR SEYCHELLES

Final Protocol

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Collectively, these contributions have ensured that the protocol reflects Seychelles' ecological context, management realities, and international best practice, while remaining accessible and adaptable for long-term, multi-institutional implementation.

Acronym

AOI	Area of Interest
CBD	Convention on Biological Diversity
CC BY 4.0	Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International (license)
CHN	Carbon–Hydrogen–Nitrogen (elemental analysis method)
CO₂	Carbon dioxide
EBV	Essential Biodiversity Variable
EEZ	Exclusive Economic Zone
EIA	Environmental Impact Assessment
EMA	Educational Marine Area(s)
EOV	Essential Ocean Variable
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable (data principles)
GCP	Ground Control Point(s)
GEO BON	Group on Earth Observations Biodiversity Observation Network
GIS	Geographic Information System
GOOS	Global Ocean Observing System
HOBO®	(Brand) Onset HOBO data logger
LOI	Loss on Ignition
MBON	Marine Biodiversity Observation Network
MPA	Marine Protected Area(s)
MSP	Marine Spatial Planning
NDC	Nationally Determined Contribution(s)
NGO	Non-Governmental Organisation(s)
OBIS	Ocean Biodiversity Information System
PAR	Photosynthetically Active Radiation
QA/QC	Quality Assurance / Quality Control
PDCS	Program Development and Coordination Section
RLE	(IUCN) Red List of Ecosystems
SCUBA	Self-Contained Underwater Breathing Apparatus
SDG	Sustainable Development Goal(s)
SfM	Structure-from-Motion
SMSP	Seychelles Marine Spatial Plan
SPGA	Seychelles Parks and Gardens Authority
tCO₂e	tonnes of CO ₂ equivalent
UAV	Unoccupied Aerial Vehicle (drone)
UNFCCC	United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change
UNEP	United Nations Environment Programme
UTM	Universal Transverse Mercator
WGS84	World Geodetic System 1984
WIO	Western Indian Ocean
WIOMSA	Western Indian Ocean Marine Science Association

Symbol

%	Percent
~	Approximately
×	“By” / multiplication (e.g., 50 × 50 m; 50 × 50 cm)
≥	Greater than or equal to
≤	Less than or equal to
>	Greater than
<	Less than
m	Metres
cm	Centimetres
m²	Square metres
km²	Square kilometres
ha	Hectares
μm	Micrometres
Mg C ha⁻¹	Megagrams (metric tonnes) of carbon per hectare
°C	Degrees Celsius
T₀	Time 0 (baseline)
T₁	Time 1 (follow-up)
X, Y	Coordinate in decimal degrees

Introduction

Seagrass ecosystems provide critical services worldwide, including habitat provision, coastal stabilization, water quality regulation, and blue carbon storage, which directly support fisheries and livelihoods¹. Their cultural, ecological, and economic importance, combined with the fact that they can be monitored at relatively low cost using methods that are feasible and applicable globally, has led to the recognition of seagrass cover, areal extent and species composition as Essential Ocean Variables (EOVs)². In Seychelles, regular monitoring of cover and composition is therefore indispensable for detecting ecological change, guiding management decisions, and supporting the nation's commitments under the Paris Agreement and national Marine Spatial Planning (MSP) frameworks. Establishing time series of percent cover is particularly valuable for tracking trends and informing adaptive management.

In Seychelles; recent national assessments have provided the first validated estimate of seagrass areal extent and carbon storage in Seychelles³. A total of 159,920 hectares (1,599 km²) of seagrass habitat were mapped across the Exclusive Economic Zone, distributed mainly on the Mahé Plateau rim, Amirantes Bank, Providence Bank, and atolls such as Desroches, Cosmoledo, and Farquhar.

Seychelles hosts (a minimum of) ~12 species of seagrass, with the highest diversity found in the inner islands (e.g., Baie Sainte Anne on Praslin, Ste Anne Marine Park, and Au Cap, Mahé), while the outer islands are dominated by extensive meadows of *Thalassodendron ciliatum* and *Thalassia hemprichii*. These meadows collectively store an estimated 18.9 million tonnes of organic carbon, equivalent to ~69 million tonnes of CO₂, making seagrass the dominant blue carbon ecosystem in Seychelles, responsible for 96% of the national blue carbon stock. Annual sequestration rates are estimated at ~510,000 tCO₂e, approximately equal to the annual emissions from Seychelles' entire energy sector. This underscores the ecological, economic, and climate significance of Seychelles' seagrass meadows and highlights the urgent need for standardized monitoring and protection measures.

In this context, this protocol establishes a standardized survey design for Seychelles, building on the Gendron's Seychelles Parks and Gardens Authority (SPGA) monitoring protocol⁴, Mortimer's Seychelles-specific guidelines⁵, and international frameworks such as SeagrassNet⁶, Seagrass-

¹ Nordlund, L., Koch, E.W., Barbier, E.B., Creed, J.C., 2016. Seagrass Ecosystem Services and Their Variability across Genera and Geographical Regions. PLoS ONE 11, e0163091. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0163091>

² Muller-Karger, F.E., Miloslavich, P., Bax, N.J., Simmons, S., Costello, M.J., Sousa Pinto, I., Canonico, G., Turner, W., Gill, M., Montes, E., Best, B.D., Pearlman, J., Halpin, P., Dunn, D., Benson, A., Martin, C.S., Weatherdon, L.V., Appeltans, W., Provoost, P., Klein, E., Kelble, C.R., Miller, R.J., Chavez, F.P., Iken, K., Chiba, S., Obura, D., Navarro, L.M., Pereira, H.M., Allain, V., Batten, S., Benedetti-Checchi, L., Duffy, J.E., Kudela, R.M., Rebelo, L.-M., Shin, Y., Geller, G., 2018. Advancing Marine Biological Observations and Data Requirements of the Complementary Essential Ocean Variables (EOVs) and Essential Biodiversity Variables (EBVs) Frameworks. Front. Mar. Sci. 5. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmars.2018.00211>

³ Rowlands, G.P., Antat, S., Baez, S.K., Cupidon, A., Faure, A., Harlay, J., Lee, C.B., Martin, L.E.C., Masque, P., Morgan, M., Mortimer, J.A., Traganos, D., 2024. The Seychelles Seagrass Mapping and Carbon Assessment. Report to the Government of Seychelles, Ministry of Agriculture, Climate Change and Environment (MACCE).

⁴ Gendron G. (2022). Seagrass Mapping and Monitoring Protocol for SPGA Managed Marine Protected Areas. Seychelles Parks and Gardens Authority.

⁵ Mortimer, J. A. (2018). Mapping, baseline assessment & monitoring protocols for seagrass habitats in the Outer Islands: Alphonse, Desroches, Farquhar, Poivre atolls. GOS-UNDP-GEF

⁶ Short, F.T., Coles, R.G., Short, C.A. (2015). SeagrassNet Manual for Scientific Monitoring of Seagrass Habitat, Worldwide edition. University of New Hampshire Publication. 73 pp.

Watch⁷ and MarineGEO⁸. The approach integrates with the Global Ocean Observing System (GOOS) and the Group on Earth Observations Biodiversity Observation Network (GEO BON), where seagrass cover and composition form the primary observations (EOVs) underpinning derived biodiversity indicators (EBVs)⁹.

Sampling Design and Sentinel Sites

The national framework is based on the establishment of 50 × 50 m Sentinel Sites across Seychelles' EEZ. Within each site, permanent fixed transects are installed to reduce variance by eliminating standing spatial heterogeneity and thereby increasing the statistical power to detect real temporal changes in seagrass cover¹⁰. This approach avoids the risk of “blind sentinels” and enables detection of ecologically significant changes of 10–20% cover at standard thresholds of significance and power.

Modular Protocol

The design follows a modular approach. The core protocol uses low-cost field methodologies (transects, quadrats, photoquadrats) to measure seagrass cover and composition, ensuring repeatability across diverse seascapes and capacity levels. Additional modules can expand monitoring to abiotic indicators and biotic indicators depending on organisation capacity and budget.

Integration with Global and National Frameworks

The long-term monitoring of seagrass EOVs in Seychelles contributes directly to national and international commitments, including the country's Nationally Determined Contributions (protection of 50% of seagrass and mangroves by 2025 and 100% by 2030), the Sustainable Development Goals (SDG 14 targets on pollution reduction, ecosystem protection, carbon sequestration, fisheries, marine protected areas, small-scale fisheries, and blue economy benefits), and the CBD Post-2020 Global Biodiversity Framework (notably Goals A and B, and targets on spatial planning, ecosystem restoration, invasive species management, sustainable use of wild species, and biodiversity knowledge-sharing). Seagrass habitats also support the objectives of the Ramsar Convention on Wetlands by contributing to national wetland inventories, demonstrating ecological and socio-economic benefits, and guiding restoration efforts for climate resilience and livelihoods. In addition, seagrass EOVs provide indicators for climate reporting under the UNFCCC, while directly informing mitigation and adaptation strategies. Finally, by enhancing scientific knowledge and linking ecosystem health to food security, coastal protection, and carbon storage, seagrass monitoring advances the outcomes of the UN Decade of Ocean Science for Sustainable Development, reinforcing the role of seagrass ecosystems in building a resilient, productive, and sustainable ocean.

7 McKenzie, L. J., Campbell, S. J., & Roder, C. A. (2003). Seagrass-Watch: Manual for mapping and monitoring seagrass resources. Department of Primary Industries, Queensland Government.

8 MarineGEO (2025). MarineGEO Seagrass Habitat Monitoring Protocol. Smithsonian Institution.

9 Miloslavich, P., Bax, N. J., Simmons, S. E., Klein, E., Appeltans, W., Aburto, Oropeza, O., ... & Shin, Y. J. (2018). Essential ocean variables for global sustained observations of biodiversity and ecosystem changes. *Global change biology*, 24(6), 2416-2433.

10 Schultz, S. T., Kruschel, C., Bakran-Petricioli, T., and Petricioli, D. (2015). Error, Power, and Blind Sentinels: The Statistics of Seagrass Monitoring. *PLoS ONE* 10, e0138378

Supporting Resources

Copies of this protocol, standardized datasheets, templates for data entry, and background literature will be made available online.

Approach

This protocol applies a modular approach to seagrass monitoring in Seychelles, ensuring compatibility with the EOVS framework while maintaining flexibility to adapt to available resources and institutional capacity. The core EOVS addressed is **Seagrass Cover and Composition**, defined as 1) areal extent, 2) percent cover, and 3) species composition indicators¹¹.

A three-tiered monitoring framework designed to balance broad national coverage with detailed, site-level ecological information.

Tier 1 – Baseline Awareness

Aims to build national awareness and community participation in seagrass conservation. Using a citizen-science approach, volunteers, students, tourists, and residents collect basic ecological observations. These activities promote stewardship while generating baseline data. A “**Seagrass Citizen Science Monitoring Protocol for Schools and Community**¹²” was developed under the RECOSS project in Seychelles, led by the Program Development and Coordination Section and the Ministry of Environment.

Tier 2 – Sentinel Site Monitoring

Tier 2 establishes a network of designated Sentinel Sites where permanent transects are monitored annually. This tier provides fine-scale, statistically robust data on seagrass condition, trends, and drivers of change, forming the core component of the national monitoring program. A Key Outcome of this tier is a network of sentinel sites providing repeatable, statistically robust data on seagrass condition and trends using EOVS for Seagrass: Percentage Cover and Species Composition.

Tier 3 – Mapping & Spatial Extent

Tier 3 integrates remote sensing and spatial analysis to assess seagrass areal extent and distribution at regional and national scales. Incorporating these technologies will fill critical information gaps and ensure the availability of consistent, landscape-level data for long-term assessment and reporting. Implementation of this tier is opportunistic, depending on available funding and institutional capacity, and should be integrated within the Environmental Impact Assessment (EIA) framework to maximise data use and cost-effectiveness.

In the Seychelles context, areal extent is an ecologically significant but challenging indicator/EOVS to monitor regularly within long-term programs. Its measurement relies on remote sensing and advanced spatial analysis, requiring sustained funding, specialised equipment, and technical expertise in GIS and remote sensing. For this reason, the protocol recommends that extent mapping be implemented as part of a broader decadal strategy, rather than as a core variable for annual sentinel monitoring.

¹¹ Global Ocean Observing System (2025). Essential Ocean Variable Specification Sheet: Seagrass cover and composition. GOOS Reference No; DOI: [to be assigned]

¹² Barret, L., & Gendron, G. (2026). Seychelles Seagrass Citizen Science Monitoring Protocol for Schools and Community. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18770912>

Tier 1 -Baseline Awareness

OBJECTIVE

To build national awareness and community capacity as the foundation for long-term seagrass stewardship.

Tier 1 represents the entry level of the Seychelles National Seagrass Monitoring Framework. Its principal objective is to mobilise community participation and enhance seagrass awareness through citizen-science and community-based monitoring. This tier establishes the foundation for national stewardship, engaging citizens, schools, NGOs, and tourism operators in the participatory observation of seagrass meadows.

By fostering a culture of shared responsibility and local engagement, Tier 1 contributes to early detection of ecological change, supports seagrass mapping initiatives, and builds public understanding of seagrass as critical ecosystems for coastal resilience, fisheries, and carbon storage. The approach aligns with Seychelles' national commitments under the Blue Economy, Marine Spatial Planning, and NDC frameworks, emphasizing inclusive management of marine habitats.

Citizen participation addresses a key limitation of traditional monitoring programmes, limited coverage and high operational cost, by enabling broad-scale data collection at minimal expense. At international scale, citizen science provides significant contributions to seagrass science, education, society, and policy, and offers novel opportunities to integrate scientific and local knowledge for conservation¹³. This participatory approach would fill crucial information gaps for Seychelles' nearshore seagrass habitats, where spatial coverage and temporal resolution remain limited.

Within this context, the RECOS project has developed a community, school, and citizen seagrass monitoring protocol that fits within the national seagrass monitoring framework coordinated by SeyCCAT. The protocol emphasises low-impact observation, inclusivity, and learning-by-doing. By linking seagrass monitoring with education, culture, and coastal use, the protocol aims to strengthen local stewardship, support national conservation objectives, and help ensure that Seychelles' seagrass meadows continue to protect coastlines, sustain biodiversity, and support communities in a changing climate.

Educational Marine Areas (EMAs) could serve as a practical, area-based tool for implementing Tier 1 of the National Seagrass Monitoring Framework by anchoring awareness, education, and citizen-science activities to clearly defined and accessible seagrass sites. The EMA model builds on internationally recognised experience originating in French Polynesia and promoted through education/conservation partnerships, with increasing recognition as an effective mechanism for linking education, citizen science, and local marine governance¹⁴. Within an EMA, shallow seagrass meadows could be proposed as living classrooms where schools, communities, NGOs, and management authorities engage in repeated, non-extractive observations and learning

¹³ Jones, B. L., Unsworth, R. K., McKenzie, L. J., Yoshida, R. L., & Cullen-Unsworth, L. C. (2018). Crowdsourcing conservation: The role of citizen science in securing a future for seagrass. *Marine pollution bulletin*, 134, 210-215:

¹⁴ Office français de la biodiversité. (2020). Guide méthodologique : Les Aires éducatives (Version 3, Septembre 2020). République Française – OFB

activities over time. This approach strengthens continuity, local ownership, and long-term engagement while complementing higher-tier monitoring through the development of ecological literacy, stewardship values, and sustained community presence.

In terms of method and tools, SeagrassSpotter has been successfully applied worldwide to identify and map threats across over 8,000 verified observations, demonstrating the value of citizen science in revealing local-scale human pressures often missed in conventional surveys¹⁵. The platform's data verification process, managed by trained researchers, ensures that uploaded records meet quality standards and contribute to scientifically robust monitoring outcomes.

In Seychelles, Tier 1 activities¹⁶ will include:

Educational and outreach initiatives: Development and dissemination of visual and interactive materials for schools, NGOs, and eco-tourism programmes to increase awareness of seagrass importance.

Community training sessions: Introductory workshops with local groups, focusing on participatory observation methods at pilot sites such as Côte d'Or (Praslin) via the RECOS project.

Simplified field observations: Use of presence/absence records, dominant species identification, and visual indicators of disturbance (e.g. anchoring scars, algal overgrowth, turbidity).

Data collection and validation: Integration of citizen uploads with the SeagrassSpotter platform for georeferenced data storage, expert validation, and image archiving.

The use of digital and community-based tools provides a cost-effective means to support long-term sentinel site monitoring (Tier 2), complementing emerging remote sensing and deep learning methods for Seychelles EEZ scale mapping¹⁷ (Tier 3). By coupling field observations with technological innovation, Tier 1 strengthens the evidence base for seagrass conservation, while empowering Seychellois citizens to become active participants in monitoring and protecting their coastal ecosystems.

¹⁵ Jones, B. L., Coals, L., Cullen-Unsworth, L. C., Lilley, R. J., Bartlett, A., & Unsworth, R. K. (2025). Mapping global threats to seagrass meadows reveals opportunities for conservation. *Environmental Research: Ecology*, 4(2), 025005.

¹⁶ Under development via the MACCE/PDCS RECOS Project in Côte d'Or, Praslin

¹⁷ Peng, J., Li, J., Ingalls, T. C., Schill, S. R., Kerner, H. R., & Asner, G. P. (2025). A novel deep learning algorithm for broad scale seagrass extent mapping in shallow coastal environments. *ISPRS Journal of Photogrammetry and Remote Sensing*, 220, 277-294.

RECOMMENDED METHOD

Two complementary approaches to seagrass monitoring are proposed, adapted to different user groups while remaining fully aligned with the RECOS project and the Seychelles National Seagrass Monitoring Framework (Tier 1).

1) School Groups and Eco-Clubs (Ages 8–14)

School-based monitoring uses a simplified field protocol suitable for children aged 8–14, focusing on seagrass presence, morphotypes, percent cover, and general meadow condition using paper datasheets and simple tools. Older students (~14+) may progressively transition to elements of the national Sentinel Site Monitoring Protocol (Tier 2).

Monitoring activity should be preceded by three classroom and field activities 1) Introduction to Seagrass, 2) Benefits of Seagrass, and 3) Threats to Seagrass which build essential knowledge, vocabulary, and observation skills using locally relevant examples from Côte d’Or and Seychelles lagoons. This preparation ensures that field monitoring is a meaningful extension of classroom learning and strengthens stewardship values.

2) Community Members, NGOs, and Tourists

Citizen-science monitoring shall be implemented using standardised observation forms and GPS-enabled digital capture (mobile phone, waterproof camera, or GoPro). The most suitable method is the sampling and data entering directly into SeagrassSpotter.

Each Seagrassspotter observation will record:

1. Site information: observer, date, GPS coordinates, location name;
2. Presence/absence of seagrass;
3. Dominant species identified (seagrass spotter offers an identification tools)
4. Photographic evidence of disturbance indicators: anchor scars, algal blooms, litter, sedimentation, grazing, anchor.

Submitted records would be reviewed from the open access SeagrassSpotter database by the Seychelles National Focal Point for Seagrass Monitoring, which performs quality-assurance and validation checks. Verified data are integrated into the National Seagrass Repository and synchronised with the global SeagrassSpotter database, ensuring interoperability and long-term storage.

SeagrassSpotter is a global citizen-science platform, accessible via website and mobile application that enables users to record and share georeferenced photographs of seagrass observations. Contributors can identify seagrasses to species level and provide optional details on habitat characteristics such as morphology, associated fauna, visible threats, and human use. The platform is designed for ease of participation and requires no prior training: users are guided through species identification and can indicate their level of confidence (“not confident,” “somewhat,” “very,” or “certain”).

Each submission is reviewed monthly by expert validators and experienced seagrass researchers to ensure data accuracy and consistency. Records found to be misidentified or located outside expected seagrass distribution ranges are flagged and excluded from the verified dataset. Validated observations contribute to an open-access global database supporting seagrass research, conservation, and education efforts across multiple spatial scales.

Project Seagrass (2020). SeagrassSpotter: A Citizen Science Platform for Global Seagrass Monitoring. Project Seagrass, Cardiff University. Available at: www.seagrassspotter.org

OUTCOMES

The expected outcomes from Tier 1 are:

1. Empowered citizens and communities actively engaged in seagrass stewardship, contributing local knowledge and observations that strengthen national monitoring and management efforts.
2. A shared national baseline on seagrass distribution and condition within Seychelles’ Exclusive Economic Zone (EEZ), derived from community-based observations and verified citizen-science data.
3. A comprehensive geo-referenced photographic database, hosted through the SeagrassSpotter platform and mirrored within the National Seagrass Data Repository, ensuring open access, traceability, and long-term data management.
4. Increased national and international visibility of Seychelles’ seagrass ecosystems, through integration of citizen-generated data into global conservation platforms and networks such as Project Seagrass, UNEP, and the Global Ocean Observing System (GOOS).

REPORTING AND DATA SHARING

All validated observations are archived within the National Seagrass Repository and cross-linked with SeagrassSpotter entries.

Summaries and maps are produced annually as part of the National Seagrass Status Report and shared with regional initiatives (WIOMSA, GOOS/MBON, OBIS).

Participating schools and community groups receive simplified feedback reports, visual dashboards, and certificates recognising their contribution to seagrass conservation.

Data contribute directly to awareness campaigns, national education curricula, and community restoration planning.

Tier 2- Seychelles Seagrass Sentinel Site Core Monitoring Program

OBJECTIVE AND DESIGN

To establish a standardized, science-based monitoring framework that tracks the long-term status of Seychelles' seagrass ecosystems, providing reliable data to guide conservation, restoration, and sustainable management, while supporting national and international commitments to biodiversity protection, climate resilience, and blue carbon accounting.

The core of this protocol is the long-term monitoring of seagrass percentage cover and species composition (Table 1; Figure 1). Supporting environmental variables (e.g., depth, water clarity, salinity, sediment type, nutrient concentrations, coastal pressures) and related seagrass variables (e.g., canopy height, epiphyte load) may be collected at the discretion of the monitoring program or implementing agency to provide additional context and strengthen interpretation.

Implemented at each Sentinel Site within a Location and Region (hierarchical design).

Figure 1. Structure of the Seychelles Seagrass Monitoring Protocol indicators.

The protocol is structured hierarchically for each Region by monitoring Location, each replicated by Site and with 3 fixed permanent Transects. The monitoring protocol adopts a fixed-plot design with permanent transects to provide statistically robust and repeatable measures of seagrass monitoring.

Site selection is focused primarily on intertidal and lower-littoral seagrass meadows, which are the most feasible for long-term national monitoring in Seychelles. The Region, Location and Site name and code must be standardized at national level and must be aligned with specific metadata including transect geolocalisation. A list of proposed Region and Location is available in Annex.

The following criteria guide the choice of Regions, Locations, Sites, and Transects (See Annex 1).

REGION

Regions may correspond to:

- Legally designated Marine Protected Areas (MPAs), such as Marine National Parks.
- Zone, MPAs and management units established through the Seychelles Marine Spatial Plan.
- Ecologically defined coastal zones (e.g., bays, reef systems, or islands) not yet under legal management, where monitoring is important for national reporting and conservation objectives.

Defining regions this way ensures flexibility: monitoring can align with existing governance while also covering priority seagrass areas outside formal protection (e.g., Côte d'Or, Baie Ste Anne).

Denis Island Marine Sustainable Use Area (DIMSUA) is defined as a **Region**

LOCATION

A defined coastal area or habitat where seagrass meadows are known to occur, and long-term monitoring is feasible.

At National scale Locations are chosen to represent the range of ecological settings (estuaries, coastal intertidal, reef intertidal, reef subtidal). They capture environmental gradients and allow condition comparisons among habitat types.

When applicable Location should be defined with a water catchment basin to connects land-based activities and pressures to seagrass condition.

DIMSUA could contain two monitoring **Location** (West and East)

SENTINEL SITE

A specific sentinel site within a monitoring location, permanently marked for repeated sampling. At each site, 3 transects and 33 quadrats are established to measure seagrass indicators. Sites provide the fine-scale, statistically robust data needed to detect temporal trends and link them back up to locations and regions.

Each Location encompass 2 **Sentinel Site** for monitoring

Sentinel Site Selection

The selection of the Sentinel Sites is a critical step to ensure that the program can reliably detect ecological change and provide management-relevant information. It must balance scientific rigor, long-term continuity, and practical feasibility following the above criteria:

Accessibility and cost-effectiveness

Sites must be practical to monitor with minimal reliance on boats and SCUBA diving.

Prioritising intertidal meadows ensures that monitoring can be conducted efficiently and cost-effectively, supporting repeat surveys over the long term.

Sites should minimise risks to field teams and intertidal monitoring reduces all inherent risk related to SCUBA diving activities and isolation related to remote island activities.

Representativeness

Selected Site should be representative/typical of the intertidal seagrass habitats and communities across each Location:

Site should contain the typical species assemblages to ensure that the monitoring network reflects the ecological heterogeneity of Seychelles' seagrass ecosystems.

Sites should be selected where seagrass cover is not excessively variable. To ensure Meadows dominated by persistent genus such as *Thalassodendron*, *Thalassia* or *Enhalus* are generally more suitable for this purpose than highly patchy colonising assemblages.

Management and feasibility criteria

Site selection should consider management priorities and operational feasibility. Criteria include accessibility for repeated surveys, alignment with SMSP and Marine Protected Areas or community co-management initiatives, and potential relevance for restoration activities.

Integration with mapping

Site selection should be guided by national-scale seagrass maps derived from remote sensing and UAV surveys to ensure that monitoring locations represent the full distribution of meadows at both regional and national scales.

Replication and spatial heterogeneity.

To account for within-habitat variability, at least two sites should be established at each location. While a greater number of sites would strengthen statistical power, replication must be balanced against funding and logistical constraints. Additional sites may be established within the same location to address local management or research needs. Such sites can support community or NGO-led monitoring, provide finer-scale information on specific stressors, or strengthen the representativeness of large and heterogeneous meadows.

Citizen involvement and ownership

Where possible, sites should allow engagement of schools, NGOs, and community groups. Citizen participation broadens capacity, promotes stewardship, and aligns with Seychelles' national conservation commitments.

Table 1. Summary of Seagrass Monitoring Indicators and Associated Protocol

Indicator	Indices	Description	Method of Measurement	Seychelles protocol
Geolocalisation	Position X, Y	Coordinates provide spatial context for mapping, tracking changes over time, and integrating geospatial datasets.	GPS units	Core (Required)
Seagrass Cover	Abundance (% cover)	Most important indicator. Abundance can respond to change on time-scales ranging from weeks to months depending on species).	Estimate the total % cover of seagrass within the quadrat	Core (Required)
Seagrass Species Composition	Community Structure (n species), Abundance (% cover)	Provides insights into resilience, indicating disturbance levels; colonizing species dominate disturbed areas, persistent species indicate stability.	Quadrat sampling, species identification (field surveys, genetic barcoding)	Core (Required)
Macroalgae¹⁸	Abundance (% cover)	Macroalgae are an environmental indicator because they can compete with and/or block light reaching seagrass leaves, therefore compounding environmental stress.	Visual surveys to estimate percentage cover within 50cm X 50 cm Quadrat.	Core (Required)
Sediment Composition	Dominant Grain Size Distribution	Sediment grain size affects seagrass growth, germination, survival, and distribution (McKenzie 2007). Coarse, sand dominated sediments limit plant growth due to increased mobility and lower nutrients. However, as finer-textured sediments increase (dominated by mud (grain size <63µm), porewater exchange with the overlaying water column decreases resulting in increased nutrient concentrations and phytotoxins such as sulphide, which can lead to seagrass loss.	Sediment grain size analysis (e.g. sieve) via coring method/ <i>In situ</i> observer estimation of grain size in order of dominance including: 1. mud. 2. Fine sand 3. Sand. 4. Coarse sand 5. Gravel.	Core (Required)
Depth	Meters (m)	Controls light availability and species zonation; influences physiological and morphological traits of seagrass.	Depth sounders, pressure sensors	Environmental (Optional)
Light	Lux, lumen, Photosynthetically Active Radiation (PAR)	Essential for photosynthesis; The maximum depth limit for seagrasses is determined largely by the depth to which sufficient light intensity for sustaining plant growth reaches the bottom, known as “compensation depth.” Finding from Collier et al., 2016 were used to recommend acute management thresholds for 12 species occurring in the Great Barrier Reef, Australia.	<i>In situ</i> temperature loggers (continuous monitoring): Onset Hobo® Light-temperature loggers / Submersible Odyssey™	Environmental (Optional)
Temperature	Celsius (°C)	Elevated water temperature can impact seagrasses through chronic effects in which elevated respiration at high temperatures can cause carbon loss and reduce growth Collier et al., 2017), while acute stress results in inhibition of photosynthesis and leaf death.	<i>In situ</i> temperature loggers (continuous monitoring): Onset Hobo® Light-temperature loggers or U22/ iBTag™ submersible temperature loggers (BCod™22L)	Environmental (Optional)

¹⁸ Synonym of Seaweed

Indicator	Indices	Description	Method of Measurement	Seychelles protocol
Epiphytes	Abundance (% cover)	Epiphytes are algae that grow (attached) on seagrass blades. Epiphytes are an environmental indicator because they can compete with and/or block light reaching seagrass leaves, therefore compounding environmental stress.	Visual surveys to estimate percentage cover using 50cm X 50 cm quadrat.	Biological (Optional)
Canopy Height	cm	Seagrass species function as typical foundation species depending on the morphological characteristics and structural complexity. Changes in canopy height can indicate shifts in nutrient availability, light conditions, grazing pressure, or disturbances such as physical damage from storms or anthropogenic activity.	Measure canopy height ignoring the tallest 20% of leaves and identify any grazing evidence. Express results as canopy height for the dominant species.	Biological (Optional)
Flower and Fruit Count	n	Indicates reproductive status. Useful for tracking seasonal and interannual variability in sexual reproduction.	Count total numbers of flower and fruit within the quadrat.	Biological (Optional)
Shoot Density	Shoot/m ²	Reflects seagrass productivity and recruitment. High density indicates healthy, actively growing meadows.	Count all shoot from each species within the quadrat/ Sub sample 0.25*0.25m if too dense.	Biological (Core for Restoration)
Survival	%	Measures the success of transplanted or restored seagrass, reflecting establishment and resilience under restoration activities.	Number of shoots at time t /Number of shoots planted *100.	Biological (Core for Restoration)
Anthropogenic Threat	Threat score (0–3 per pressure); Total impact index (sum of scores)	Assesses the presence and intensity of human-related pressures within or adjacent to the Sentinel Site that may directly or indirectly affect seagrass condition. Captures physical disturbance, pollution, boating and anchoring, sedimentation, fishing activity, and nearby coastal development to support interpretation of biological indicators and restoration outcomes.	Observers complete a standardised checklist for defined pressure categories (e.g. physical damage, anchoring/boating, pollution, sedimentation, fishing/gleaning, coastal works) and assign a score from 0 (absent) to 3 (high) based on observed evidence. Impacts are documented using photographs and GPS points. Scores are summed to derive a total impact index for the site.	Biological (Core for Restoration)
Organic Carbon Content	Mg C ha ⁻¹	Organic carbon stored in seagrass biomass (above- and below-ground) and underlying sediments. It serves as a key indicator for assessing blue carbon stocks and sequestration potential. Measurements provide baseline data for national greenhouse gas inventories, restoration assessments, and carbon accounting under international frameworks.	Follow standardized protocols from Howard et al. (2014) ¹⁹ for coastal blue carbon assessment. Soil depth in Cm could be used as a proxy	Blue Carbon

¹⁹ Howard, J., Hoyt, S., Isensee, K., Pidgeon, E., & Telszewski, M. (Eds.). (2014). Coastal Blue Carbon: Methods for Assessing Carbon Stocks and Emissions Factors in Coastal Ecosystems. Conservation International, Intergovernmental Oceanographic Commission of UNESCO, International Union for Conservation of Nature.

Seagrass Monitoring Protocol – Core

BEFORE DEPARTURE – PREPARATION

1. Review the monitoring schedule, protocols and monitored indicators
2. Confirm the sentinel site, location, and region code and metadata (Annex 2)
3. Review and pack the full equipment list
4. Localise **Permanent Marker (See Note)**²⁰ of Sentinel Site
5. Start GPS tracking and take a picture of GPS date and time

Equipment List

	1 × 50 m fibreglass measuring tapes (Minimum)
	1 × GPS
	Compass
	1 × standard quadrat (50 × 50 cm)
	3 × monitoring datasheets (waterproof paper or slates) based on datasheet in Annex 3.
	3 × Pencils
	1 × 30 cm ruler
	1 × Camera with fully charged batteries and sufficient memory/disk space available
	Percent cover standard sheets (calibration photo guides)
	Seagrass identification sheet or App

²⁰ **Permanent Marker Note:** To minimise physical disturbance to seagrass beds, permanent markers for sentinel sites should preferentially rely on existing natural features at the location (e.g., stable rock outcrops) where feasible and clearly identifiable.

Where natural features are not suitable or sufficiently stable, artificial markers may be installed using a rebar stake with a surface or subsurface buoy. In such cases, the following best practices apply:

- Select placement that avoids dense or sensitive seagrass patches and minimises trampling during installation and subsequent access.
- Use a rebar of appropriate diameter and corrosion resistance.
- Ensure the rebar is firmly driven into the substrate to a minimum depth of 50 cm to guarantee long-term stability and reduce the risk of movement or scour.
- Keep the surface footprint minimal and clearly mark the location to prevent repeated repositioning.

TRANSECT AND QUADRAT PLACEMENT (REQUIRED)

A – TRANSECT PLACEMENT

1. Place or Locate the **permanent marker (See Note)¹⁸** for the site (origin point of the transect).
2. Start GPS tracking and take a picture of GPS date and time
3. Set the compass bearing:
 - a. Use a bearing perpendicular to the shoreline, oriented from shallow to deeper water.
 - b. Read the compass accurately and record the bearing on the data sheet.
4. Lay out the 50 m transect line along the recorded compass bearing. Ensure the tape is taut and follows a straight line (Figure 2).

B - RECORD TRANSECT METADATA

At the beginning of the transect, Record:

- | | |
|--|--|
| 5. Site code | 10. GPS coordinates at the end (50 m) -
In Decimal Degrees to 5 decimal
places (e.g. -4.12345, 45.12345) |
| 6. Transect number | 11. Compass bearing used. |
| 7. Observer names and organisations
(full name + surname) | 12. Take a picture of the slate |
| 8. Date | |
| 9. GPS coordinates at the start (0 m) -
In Decimal Degrees to 5 decimal
places (e.g. -4.12345, 45.12345) | |

C - QUADRAT PLACEMENT AND MEASUREMENT

13. Quadrats are placed on the right side of the transect line.
14. **Place 11 quadrats at 5 m intervals:** 0 m, 5 m, 10 m, ... 50 m
15. Always start at 0 m to maintain consistent sampling.
16. At each quadrat position:
 - Take a **photograph of the quadrat** before taking any other measurements.
 - Take photo before disturbing sediment (avoid resuspension).
 - Collect data for Indicator 1, 2 and 3(Required).
 - Collect data for optional indicators

D - SECOND TRANSECT PLACEMENT

17. From the permanent marker, measure 25 m to the left.
18. Mark the starting point and lay the transect using the same compass bearing as Transect 1.
19. Repeat all procedures from Sections B to C

E-THIRD TRANSECT PLACEMENT

20. From the permanent marker, measure 25 m to the right.
21. Lay the transect along the same compass bearing.
22. Repeat all procedures from Sections B to C
- 23. Move to next Sentinel Site – Repeat from Section A**

Frequency: Bi annual during the calm season (April-May) and (October-November).

Figure 2..Example of a Sentinel Site with three permanent fixed transects (50 m in length, spaced 25 m apart) established in an *Enhalus acoroides* seagrass meadow at Baie Sainte Anne, Praslin.

INDICATOR 1. SEAGRASS COVER (REQUIRED) AND 2. MACROALGAE COVER (REQUIRED)

Unit: Percent cover (%)

Equipment: Quadrat (50 × 50 cm), percent cover photo guides (calibration sheets), clipboard, datasheet and camera.

Definition: Seagrass cover and macroalgae cover are estimated separately by visual assessment. Because they can overlap, their combined total may exceed 100%.

“Plant cover” is defined as the relative area of a species when projected vertically onto the substrate surface, irrespective of whether the species forms the uppermost canopy or occurs beneath other vegetation²¹. Plant cover must not be confused with top cover (canopy cover), which records only the uppermost visible layer.

Because plant cover accounts for overlapping vegetation layers, the sum of cover values across species or functional groups may exceed 100%. For example, a species may have substantial plant cover while having a top cover of zero if it occurs entirely beneath another canopy.

Cover Categories:

At each quadrat, cover is estimated separately for the following categories (See Annex. Benthic Category):

- Seagrass (by species)
- Macroalgae
- Abiotic
- Other visible benthic features (See Annex 4.)

Procedure - Seagrass Cover:

1. After photographing the quadrat, visually estimate total seagrass plant cover, defined as the percentage of the quadrat area occupied by all seagrass leaves and shoots when projected onto the substrate, regardless of whether they are overlain by macroalgae or other vegetation.
2. If total seagrass cover is < 3%, count all visible seagrass shoots within the quadrat and convert to cover using the agreed approximation: 1 shoot ≈ 0.1% cover (species- and size-dependent).
3. Record total seagrass plant cover (%).
4. Identify all seagrass species present in the quadrat in accordance with Indicator 2 (Seagrass Species Composition).
5. For each seagrass species, directly estimate and record its plant cover (%), based on the total area of that species within the quadrat (see Figure 3).
6. Ensure that the sum of species-specific seagrass covers equals the total seagrass plant cover (%).

²¹ Wilson, J. B. (2011). Cover plus: Ways of measuring plant canopies and the terms used for them. *Journal of Vegetation Science*

Procedure - MacroAlgae Cover:

1. From above the quadrat, estimate % cover of **macroalgae**.
2. Macroalgae may:
 - a. Cover bare substrate, and/or
 - b. Overlie seagrass canopies.
3. Record total macroalgae plant cover (%) using the same visual estimation method and photo guides.

Procedure – Other Cover Categories

1. Estimate and record cover (%) for other visible features following the same projection principle.
2. These categories are recorded independently and may overlap with seagrass or macroalgae cover where applicable.

Frequency: At every quadrat (11 quadrats per transect, 3 transect per Site, each monitoring event).

Methodological Notes

Cover values represent total area, not canopy dominance.

Because vegetation may overlap, total cover across all categories and species may exceed 100%.

Plant cover is particularly appropriate for assessing total vegetation presence and persistence, while canopy/top cover is more appropriate for assessing dominance and light obstruction (Wilson, 2011).

Figure 3. Seagrass Percentage Cover Calibration Sheet from Seagrass Watch.

INDICATOR 3: SEAGRASS SPECIES COMPOSITION (REQUIRED)

Unit: Percent composition (%) of each species within total seagrass cover

Linked indicator: Indicator 1 – Plant Cover

Equipment: Quadrat (50 × 50 cm), seagrass identification sheet, clipboard & datasheet, camera.

Procedure:

1. **Identify all seagrass species** in the quadrat according to the technical skills of your field team. Some teams may wish to use the Kreol Names for the five morphotypes of seagrasses as follows:
 - Gomon zerb gran fey: *Enhalus acoroides*
 - Gomon zerb torti: *Thalassia hemprichii*, *Oceana serrulata*, *Cymodocea rotundata*, *Halodule uninervis*;
 - Gomon zerb levantay: *Thalassodendron ciliatum*;
 - Gomon zerb sed (or Gomon zerb spageti): *Syringodium isoetifolium*;
 - Gomon zerb pti fey oval (or Gomon zerb zorey lapen or Gomon zerb papiyon): *Halophila decipiens*, *Halophila stipulacea*, *Halophila ovalis* (complex) when conducting species assessments (See Annex Benthic Category).

Other teams with better knowledge of seagrass taxonomy may want to identify each species using scientific nomenclature (Latin names).

2. Estimate the plant cover (%) of each seagrass species or morphotypes/Kreol Names, based on its total area within the quadrat.
3. Use the seagrass ID sheet and check multiple features for accuracy.
4. Ensure that the **sum of species-specific seagrass plant cover values equals the total seagrass plant cover (%)** recorded under Indicator 1.

Frequency: At every quadrat (11 quadrats per transect, 3 transect per Site, each monitoring event).

Note: Resources for identifying seagrasses are available from

- SeagrassSpotter (<https://seagrassspotter.org/identify>).
- SeagrassWatch (<https://www.seagrasswatch.org/idseagrass/>).
- The Seek app by iNaturalist (https://www.inaturalist.org/pages/seek_app) may be helpful in identifying other common sessile organisms.
- Easy Guide to Identify Seagrasses of Seychelles and the Wider Western Indian Ocean. Mortimer, J.A. (in press). SeyCCAT
- Mortimer, J.A., Watson, M-F, Faure, A. (in press). Guide to Identifying Seagrass Species of Seychelles. SeyCCAT.

LIST OF SEAGRASS SPECIES AND ASSOCIATED MORPHOTYPES

Enhalus acoroides
Gomon zerb gran fey

Thalassodendron ciliatum
Gomon zerb levantay

Syringodium isoetifolium
Gomon zerb sed (or Gomon zerb spageti)

Thalassia hemprichii

Oceana serrulata

Cymodocea rotundata

Halodule uninervis

Gomon zerb torti

Halophila decipiens

Halophila stipulacea

Halophila ovalis (complex)

Gomon zerb pti fey oval (or Gomon zerb zorey lapen, or Gomon zerb papiyon)

INDICATOR 4: SEDIMENT TYPE (REQUIRED)

Unit: The descriptors relate to the size of the sediment grains: gravel (>2000 µm); coarse sand (>500 µm); sand (>250 µm); fine sand (>63 µm); and mud (<63 µm).

Definition: Sediment type refers to the dominant grain size of the surface sediment, determined by tactile assessment of the uppermost sediment layer. Classification is based on particle size.

Equipment: Quadrat (50 × 50 cm) & datasheet.

Procedure:

1. At each quadrat, insert fingers into the top 1 cm of substrate and feel texture.
2. Record dominant grain size category (see Figure 4):
 - Mud – smooth, sticky;
 - Fine sand – smooth, slight roughness;
 - Sand – rough grainy texture, distinguishable particles;
 - Coarse sand – coarse, loose particles;
 - Gravel – very coarse with small stones.
3. Do not use mixed descriptors (e.g., Sandymud, MuddySand).

Recording Sediment origin / composition: If the origin or composition of the sediment is evident (e.g. biogenic carbonate from dead *Halimeda* sp., coral rubble, shell hash), this information may be recorded as a note in the comments section. Coral rubble should be included under the Abiotic category and is defined as mechanically or chemically abraded fragments of reef-building organisms or reef rock that are larger than the sand fraction; its presence should be specified in the Notes or cover sample notes field of the datasheet.

Frequency: At every quadrat (11 quadrats per transect, 3 transect per Site, each monitoring event)

Figure 4. Sediment type based on size of grain

Protocol for Biological Indicators -Optional Modules

INDICATOR 5: CANOPY HEIGHT (OPTIONAL)

Unit: Centimetres (cm) – average leaf length of dominant species.

Equipment: 30 cm ruler (or flexible measuring tape), clipboard & datasheet, quadrat (50 × 50 cm).

Procedure:

1. Identify the **dominant seagrass species** (highest % cover) in the quadrat.
2. Randomly select a **clump of leaf blades** and measure canopy height, ignoring the tallest 20%.
3. Extend each leaf to maximum length/height (without uprooting) and measure from the substrate to the leaf tip.
4. Take **three replicate measurements** within the quadrat and record all values.
5. If density is very low and no clump can be formed, measure **five individual shoots** of the dominant species and calculate the average height.
6. Record the average canopy height (cm) on the datasheet.

Frequency: At every quadrat (11 quadrats per transect, each monitoring event).

INDICATOR 6: ESTIMATE EPIPHYTE COVER (OPTIONAL)

Unit: % cover

Equipment: Quadrat (50 × 50 cm)

Procedure:

1. Estimate average % leaf surface covered, then multiply by % of leaves affected.
2. Example: 20% of blades × 50% coverage each = 10% epiphyte cover.
3. Use the epiphyte cover matrix to assist. Record the average canopy height (cm) on the datasheet.

	0	1	5	10	15	20	25	30	35	40	45	50	55	60	65	70	75	80	85	90	95	100
0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
5	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	2	2	2	2	3	3	3	3	4	4	4	4	5	5	5
10	1	1	1	1	2	2	3	3	4	4	5	5	6	6	7	7	8	8	9	9	10	10
15	1	1	2	2	3	4	5	5	6	7	8	8	9	10	11	11	12	13	14	14	15	15
20	1	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	20
25	1	1	3	4	5	6	8	9	10	11	13	14	15	16	18	19	20	21	23	24	25	25
30	1	2	3	5	6	8	9	11	12	14	15	17	18	20	21	23	24	26	27	29	30	30
35	1	2	4	5	7	9	11	12	14	16	18	19	21	23	25	26	28	30	32	33	35	35
40	1	2	4	6	8	10	12	14	16	18	20	22	24	26	28	30	32	34	36	38	40	40
45	1	2	5	7	9	11	14	16	18	20	23	25	27	29	32	34	36	38	41	43	45	45
50	1	3	5	8	10	13	15	18	20	23	25	28	30	33	35	38	40	43	45	48	50	50
55	1	3	6	8	11	14	17	19	22	25	28	30	33	36	39	41	44	47	50	52	55	55
60	1	3	6	9	12	15	18	21	24	27	30	33	36	39	42	45	48	51	54	57	60	60
65	1	3	7	10	13	16	20	23	26	29	33	36	39	42	46	49	52	55	59	62	65	65
70	1	4	7	11	14	18	21	25	28	32	35	39	42	46	49	53	56	60	63	67	70	70
75	1	4	8	11	15	19	23	26	30	34	38	41	45	49	53	56	60	64	68	71	75	75
80	1	4	8	12	16	20	24	28	32	36	40	44	48	52	56	60	64	68	72	76	80	80
85	1	4	9	13	17	21	26	30	34	38	43	47	51	55	60	64	68	72	77	81	85	85
90	1	5	9	14	18	23	27	32	36	41	45	50	54	59	63	68	72	77	81	86	90	90
95	1	5	10	14	19	24	29	33	38	43	48	52	57	62	67	71	76	81	86	90	95	95
100	1	5	10	15	20	25	30	35	40	45	50	55	60	65	70	75	80	85	90	95	100	100

INDICATOR 7: FLOWER AND FRUIT COUNT (OPTIONAL)

Unit: Numbers of Flowers and Numbers of fruits

Equipment: Quadrat (50 × 50 cm)

Procedure:

1. Check each species for the presence of fruit or flower, if present take a photo
2. If Yes, Count the number total of fruit and flower for each species within the quadrat

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²² Gole, S., Kuppusamy, S., Das, H., & Johnson, J. A. (2023). Flowering and fruiting of Tape Seagrass *Enhalus acoroides* (Lf) Royle from the Andaman Islands: observations from inflorescence buds to dehiscent fruits. *Journal of Threatened Taxa*, 15(1), 22494-22500.

INDICATOR 8: SHOOT DENSITY (OPTIONAL)

Unit: shoots/ m²

Equipment: Quadrat (50 × 50 cm)

Procedure:

1. Count all shoot from each species within the quadrat.
2. Sub sample 0.25*0.25m if too dense.

Frequency: At every quadrat (11 quadrats per transect, each monitoring event)

INDICATOR 9: SURVIVAL

Unit: Percentage (%) of surviving shoots

Equipment: Quadrat (50 × 50 cm), Tagged plots

Procedure:

1. Mark and record the number of shoots or planting units at the time of transplantation (T_0).
2. During subsequent monitoring events, count the number of surviving shoots (T_1).
3. Calculate survival percentage using the formula: $\text{Survival (\%)} = (\text{Shoots at } T_1 / \text{Shoots planted at } T_0) \times 100$
4. Record any observations of mortality causes (e.g., sediment burial, grazing, uprooting).

Frequency: Monitor survival at each designated restoration plot during every scheduled monitoring event (e.g., 1 month, 3 months, 6 months, and 12 months post-transplantation), then annually once plots have stabilized.

INDICATOR 10: ANTHROPOGENIC THREAT

Unit: Threat score (0–3 per pressure); Total Impact Index (sum of scores).

Equipment: Clipboard & standardised threat-assessment datasheet, GPS or GPS-enabled tablet/smartphone, digital camera.

Procedure:

1. Define the assessment area as the Sentinel Site and its immediate surroundings (including a buffer adapted to site context).
2. Conduct the assessment concurrently with biological surveys to ensure consistency in environmental conditions.
3. Visually inspect the site for evidence of human-related pressures, including physical damage to seagrass (e.g. scarring, trampling), boating and anchoring activity, pollution and litter, sedimentation or turbidity linked to human activities, fishing or gleaning, and nearby coastal development or works.
4. For each pressure category, assign a score from 0 to 3 based on observed evidence:
 - 0 = absent
 - 1 = low
 - 2 = moderate
 - 3 = high
5. Document all observed impacts using GPS points and photographs, noting brief descriptions where relevant.
6. Sum the individual pressure scores to calculate the Total Impact Index for the Sentinel Site and record the result on the datasheet.

Frequency: Once per monitoring event at each Sentinel Site, conducted alongside seagrass biological measurements; additional assessments may be undertaken following major disturbance events (e.g. storms, coastal works).

Protocol for Environmental Indicators - Optional Modules

INDICATOR 11: DEPTH

Units: meters (m)

Equipment:

- Depth sounder
- Pressure sensor (submersible)
- Measuring pole (backup, for shallow intertidal sites)

Procedure:

- Record water depth at each transect start (0 m), midpoint (25 m), and end (50 m).
- Use depth sounder or pressure sensor for subtidal meadows.
- For intertidal sites during tidal exposure, record the time and tidal height from local tide charts.
- Note conditions (e.g., spring tide, neap tide, wave exposure).

Frequency: Each monitoring event.

INDICATOR 12: LIGHT

Units: Lux, Lumen, Photosynthetically Active Radiation (PAR; $\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{d}^{-1}$)

Equipment: In situ light loggers:

- Onset HOBO® light-temperature loggers (Figure 5).
- Submersible Odyssey™ PAR loggers.

Procedure:

1. Deploy logger(s) at mid-meadow depth secured to a star picket or rebar stake.
2. Ensure sensors are above sediment surface and unobstructed.
3. Program for continuous logging (10–30 min intervals).
4. Retrieve loggers every 3–6 months for data download and battery replacement.
5. Calibrate against PAR standards when possible.

Frequency: Continuous monitoring. Review datasets seasonally.

Figure 5. HOBO light-temperature logger

INDICATOR 13: TEMPERATURE

Units: Celsius °C

Equipment:

In situ temperature loggers (Figure 6):

- Onset HOBO® light-temperature loggers
- Onset HOBO Water Temperature Pro v2 Data Logger²³
- OceanLabs Remote Sensing buoy

Procedure:

1. Install logger at mid-meadow depth, attached securely near permanent transect marker.
2. Ensure logger is shaded from direct sunlight but exposed to water column.
3. Program for continuous recording (30–60 min intervals).
4. Retrieve every 3–6 months to download data.

Frequency: Continuous monitoring. Review datasets seasonally.

Figure 6. Left - HOBO temperature logger U22, Right - OceanLab Buoy

²³ <https://www.onsetcomp.com/products/data-loggers/u22-001?srsId=AfmBOorbrotJwOSu3mBeQ2AmGlZ4bBvdsxAGoD4477FT5GCZRE8e22d>

Protocol for Blue Carbon Indicator - Optional Modules

INDICATOR 14: ORGANIC CARBON CONTENT

Unit: Megagrams of carbon per hectare (Mg C ha⁻¹)

Equipment: Sediment corer (minimum 30 cm depth), sample bags or tubes, drying oven (60°C), mortar and pestle or grinder, analytical balance, Elemental Analyzer (CHN) or muffle furnace (for Loss on Ignition method), desiccator, and data sheets.

Procedure:

Sampling: Collect sediment cores (minimum 30 cm depth) from representative points within seagrass meadows. Record GPS position, sediment depth, and seagrass characteristics.

Sample Preparation: Dry samples to constant weight (60°C), grind to a fine, homogenous powder, and sieve to remove debris.

Laboratory Analysis:

- Preferred: Determine % organic carbon using an Elemental Analyzer (CHN method).
- Alternative: Use Loss on Ignition (LOI) by combusting dried sediment at 550°C for 4 hours and calculating % organic matter, then converting to %C using a standard factor.

Calculation:

- Carbon density (g C cm⁻³) = %C × bulk density.
- Carbon stock (Mg C ha⁻¹) = Carbon density × depth × area.

Data Recording: Record all sample metadata, including site, date, core depth, and analytical method used.

Frequency: Baseline measurement at initial survey for each monitoring site, followed by reassessment every 5–10 years or after major disturbances or restoration interventions.

For More Details see Howard, J., Hoyt, S., Isensee, K., Pidgeon, E., & Telszewski, M. (Eds.). (2014). *Coastal Blue Carbon: Methods for Assessing Carbon Stocks and Emissions Factors in Coastal Ecosystems*. Conservation International, Intergovernmental Oceanographic Commission of UNESCO, International Union for Conservation of Nature.

Data Submission Procedure

1. Review field datasheets for completeness

- Review all field datasheets in the field or immediately after sampling, while observations are still fresh. Verify that:
- All required fields are completed (observer names, date in an unambiguous format, site code and site name);
- Species names or codes are legible and unambiguous to a reader not present during data collection;
- Any unclear entries are corrected or clarified before leaving the site.

2. Preserve field records

- Rinse and allow field datasheets to dry.
- Photograph each completed datasheet and retain both paper and electronic copies in local project archives.

3. Data entry into the standardised spreadsheet

- Enter all observations into the standardised data entry spreadsheet corresponding to the monitoring site and survey. Complete all associated metadata fields (protocol details, sampling event information, and methodological notes).
- Do not rename existing columns or create new columns.
- Use the designated Notes fields to record additional context, clarifications, or deviations from standard procedures.

4. Species codes and taxonomic entries

The spreadsheet may be pre-filled with species codes and taxonomic information from previous surveys. If additional species are recorded:

- Assign a new, unique species code;
- Enter the full scientific name (or the closest confident taxonomic identification) in the relevant reference sheet;
- Ensure that newly created codes do not duplicate existing codes.

5. Data submission

Submit the completed spreadsheet, together with scanned field datasheets, to National Focal Point following the agreed project data submission schedule and file-naming conventions.

6. Support and clarification

For questions regarding data entry, metadata completion, or submission procedures, contact Bee Ecological Consulting through the designated project focal point.

Tier 3- Mapping and Aerial Extent

OBJECTIVE AND DESIGN

To provide information on seagrass extent and distribution within Seychelles' territorial waters and Exclusive Economic Zone (EEZ).

The Tier 3 aims to generate Seychelles' contribution to the EOVS: Seagrass Areal Extent under GOOS defined as the total horizontal area occupied by seagrass meadows, expressed in square kilometres (km²). Mapping should delineate continuous and patchy beds, differentiating seagrass from bare substrate, macroalgae, or coral reef.

This tier complements the field-based sentinel monitoring under Tier 1 and Tier 2, providing coverage through geospatial mapping and analysis.

The Tier 3 mapping component is required for international reporting thus, a national update strategy is recommended including:

- Partial updates every 5 years using project based and EIA data;
- Full national reassessment every 10 years.

This strategy should be developed in consultation with national institutions due to the high cost and technical demands of implementation.

RECOMMENDED METHODS

Seagrass areal extent can be estimated using multiple complementary approaches. Each varies in scale, accuracy, and cost, and may be combined to improve reliability. Field observations should always be paired with corresponding metadata describing the method, spatial resolution, and accuracy.

Option 1 – Field Perimeter Mapping (*In Situ* GPS Survey)

Mapping teams delineate seagrass meadow boundaries using a handheld GPS or GPS-enabled tablet while visually tracing the perimeter of the meadow from a boat or while snorkelling. This method provides groundtruthed mapping and allows field observers to distinguish seagrass from optically similar substrates such as macroalgae. However, it is time-intensive and limited to shallow or easily accessible areas, and therefore not practical for deep-water or extensive meadows.

Workflow Overview

1. Identify seagrass bed from recent imagery or local knowledge.
2. Trace the perimeter using a handheld GPS or GPS-enabled tablet while walking, snorkelling, or boating.
3. Record coordinates at regular intervals; capture geotagged photos noting dominant species and percent cover.
4. Import GPS tracks into GIS to generate polygons and calculate area.
5. Store results in WGS84 / UTM Zone 40S, including full metadata (observer, date, accuracy, method).

Option 2 – Remote Sensing (Satellite or Aerial Imagery)

This method is applied for regional and national-scale assessments, providing broad spatial coverage of seagrass habitats. Seagrass extent can be mapped using remote sensing imagery acquired from airborne or space-borne platforms, including aerial photographs, unoccupied aerial vehicles (UAVs), and satellite sensors. Imagery acquisition should balance spatial resolution, spectral characteristics (number of bands), cloud cover, and cost. Freely available sources include Sentinel-2 (European Space Agency/Copernicus) and Landsat (NASA and the US Geological Survey), while high-resolution commercial satellites such as WorldView-2/3, PlanetScope, and Pleiades offer greater detail at higher cost. Data processing, classification, and modelling can be efficiently conducted through cloud-based platforms such as Google Earth Engine or equivalent remote-sensing analysis environments.

This approach enables consistent, repeatable, and scalable mapping of seagrass extent to support temporal comparison, national reporting, and ecosystem monitoring. However, accuracy can be affected by water turbidity, depth, and bottom reflectance, and therefore requires technical expertise and validation with field data to ensure reliable results.

Workflow Overview:

1. Acquire cloud-free imagery (Sentinel-2, PlanetScope, WorldView) at low tide.
2. Apply atmospheric and radiometric corrections.
3. Use supervised or object-based classification to map seagrass extent.
4. Validate using groundtruthed field data (e.g. Tier 2) or citizen-science records (Tier 1) and compute accuracy metrics (Overall, User's, Producer's).
5. Convert raster outputs to vector polygons and attribute by site, date, sensor, and method.

Option 3 – GIS-based *ex situ* (Desktop Digitising / Visual Interpretation using Google/ESRI Basemaps)

This option maps seagrass areal extent through expert-led visual interpretation and digitising directly in a GIS software (QGIS, ArcGIS), using high-resolution basemaps (e.g., Google basemap imagery or ESRI World Imagery). In Seychelles, shallow seagrass meadows can often be distinguishable due to generally oligotrophic waters and high water clarity in sheltered lagoons and intertidal flats. However, reliable interpretation requires strong local knowledge and habitat-specific expertise to discriminate seagrass from optically similar features (e.g., coral reef structure, coral rubble and macroalgae meadows). This approach is best applied as a rapid, low-cost screening and baseline delineation method, and should be paired with targeted field validation (Tier 2) to correct misclassification.

Key strengths include rapid coverage of multiple bays/islands without field mobilisation, repeatability for change detection when imagery dates are comparable, and direct generation of GIS-ready polygons for national reporting. Limitations include uncertainty in imagery acquisition date/tide state, variable water column effects (sun glint, depth, haze), and potential confusion between benthic classes where spectral/texture contrast is low.

Workflow Overview

1. Select the clearest Google or ESRI basemap imagery and define the AOI.
2. Digitise seagrass extent by expert visual interpretation, distinguishing seagrass from coral reef structures and macroalgae.
3. Attribute polygons (site, date, imagery source, confidence).
4. Validate with targeted Tier 1/2 field or photo data.
5. Calculate area and archive outputs with metadata.

Option 4 – Unoccupied Aerial Vehicle (Drone) Mapping

This option is particularly suited for small seagrass meadows, restoration sites, and areas subject to development or ecological assessment where high spatial detail is required. UAV (drone) surveys provide very high-resolution imagery (≤ 10 cm), enabling precise mapping of seagrass boundaries, species composition, and condition. Imagery is typically acquired at altitudes between 30–150 m with at least 70% overlap and processed using Structure-from-Motion (SfM) photogrammetry to generate orthomosaics²⁴. UAV mapping offers a powerful tool for local management, restoration planning, and impact monitoring due to its spatial precision and flexibility. However, the method is limited by restricted coverage per flight, weather dependency, and the need for specialized equipment and technical expertise.

In Seychelles, UAV-based mapping should be integrated within the Environmental Impact Assessment framework, ensuring that coastal and marine development projects requiring baseline habitat information contribute standardized, georeferenced seagrass data. These locally collected datasets can feed into the national seagrass repository, supporting periodic updates of areal extent and enhancing national reporting capacity.

Workflow Overview:

1. Capture imagery at 30–150 m altitude (≤ 10 cm resolution) with $\geq 70\%$ overlap.
2. Process orthomosaics using Structure-from-Motion (SfM) photogrammetry, incorporating ground control points (GCPs).
3. Digitize or classify seagrass presence and validate with field quadrats.
4. Import results into GIS, calculate meadow area, and archive within the National Seagrass Repository.

EXPECTED OUTCOMES

The expected outcomes from Tier 3 are:

1. National, regional, and local seagrass maps generated, providing a spatial record of seagrass extent, distribution, and change across Seychelles' territorial waters and EEZ.

²⁴ Hamad, I.Y., Staehr, P.A.U., Rasmussen, M.B., Sheikh, M., 2022. Drone-Based Characterization of Seagrass Habitats in the Tropical Waters of Zanzibar. *Remote Sensing* 14, 680. <https://doi.org/10.3390/rs14030680>

2. Periodic updates to national datasets through a structured cycle, partial updates every 5 years using EIA and project-based data, and a full national reassessment every 10 years, ensuring Seychelles meets its NDC international reporting commitments.
3. Integration of Tier 3 mapping within the Environmental Impact Assessment framework, requiring that all coastal and marine development projects collect and share georeferenced seagrass extent data in line with national standards.
4. Strengthened decision-making capacity for agencies managing MPAs, coastal planning, and blue-carbon initiatives through easy access to validated spatial layers and standardized metadata.

Restoration Protocol

This step-by-step protocol outlines best practices for the restoration of seagrass habitats in Seychelles. Building on Kilminster et al. (2015)²⁵, restoration must distinguish between colonizing/opportunistic species (which recover quickly but provide limited stability) and persistent species (slower-growing but more resilient over decades). Persistent species are critical for climate mitigation and ecosystem services, yet they are also vulnerable to anthropogenic disturbance (e.g. Coastal development) and require targeted interventions.

Focusing restoration on persistent species such as *Enhalus acoroides*, *Thalassodendron ciliatum*, and *Thalassia hemprichii* all of which are characterized by dense, woody root mats that provide ecosystem stability and ensures that national-scale investments align with long-term ecosystem resilience rather than short-term vegetation cover. These species form the ecological backbone of Seychelles' meadows and are recommended priority candidates for national-scale restoration. The UNEP/WIOMSA Seagrass Restoration Guidelines²⁶ reinforce this by recommending that restoration prioritize species with high structural and functional value, carefully selecting donor sites to prevent degradation, and ensuring genetic and hydrodynamic considerations are incorporated. In particular, the guidelines emphasize the importance of adaptive management, post-restoration monitoring, and capacity-building at community and institutional levels, all of which are essential if Seychelles is to operationalize restoration at scale.

Restoration efforts must be elevated beyond site-based projects to form part of a national strategy, in line with Seychelles' commitments under its NDCs to protect 100% of seagrass ecosystems by 2030.

Accordingly, the national protocol proposes that:

1. Donor-site selection follows stringent ecological safeguards to avoid damage to intact meadows.
2. Techniques (vegetative transplantation, rhizome fragments, or seed-based methods) are selected based on species traits, sediment depth, and hydrodynamic conditions.
3. Monitoring frameworks are standardized to evaluate success.
4. Scaling-up restoration is embedded in a tiered national strategy: pilot interventions at sentinel sites (e.g. Baie Ste Anne) inform broader application across the EEZ, ensuring lessons learned are transferable across islands.

Overall, Seychelles' restoration strategy should be science-based, nationally coordinated, and adaptive, combining global best practices^{27 28} with regional guidelines to ensure that restored

²⁵ Kilminster, K., McMahon, K., Waycott, M., Kendrick, G. A., Scanes, P., McKenzie, L., ... & Udy, J. (2015). Unravelling complexity in seagrass systems for management: Australia as a microcosm. *Science of the Total Environment*, 534, 97-109.

²⁶ UNEP-Nairobi Convention/WIOMSA. (2020). Guidelines for seagrass ecosystem restoration in the Western Indian Ocean Region. UNEP, Nairobi. 63 pp. Available at: www.nairobiconvention.org; www.wiomsa.org

²⁷ Ambo-Rappe, R., La Nafie, Y.A., Syafiuddin, Limbong, S.R., Asriani, N., Handayani, N.T., Lisdayanti, E., 2019. Short Communication: Restoration of seagrass *Enhalus acoroides* using a combination of generative and vegetative techniques. *Biodiversitas* 20. <https://doi.org/10.13057/biodiv/d201132>

²⁸ Tan, Y.M., Dalby, O., Kendrick, G.A., Statton, J., Sinclair, E.A., Fraser, M.W., Macreadie, P.I., Gillies, C.L., Coleman, R.A., Waycott, M., Van Dijk, K., Vergés, A., Ross, J.D., Campbell, M.L., Matheson, F.E., Jackson, E.L., Irving, A.D., Govers, L.L., Connolly, R.M., McLeod, I.M., Rasheed, M.A., Kirkman, H., Flindt, M.R., Lange, T., Miller, A.D., Sherman, C.D.H., 2020. Seagrass Restoration Is Possible: Insights and Lessons From Australia and New Zealand. *Front. Mar. Sci.* 7, 617. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmars.2020.00617>

meadows are not only re-established but also persist and thrive under changing climatic and anthropogenic pressures.

RESTORATION SITE SUITABILITY KEY

Within a national framework for seagrass restoration, the decision to proceed with planting must be based on an evidence-based, standardized and transparent assessment of site suitability. The UNEP/WIOMSA guidelines recommend that restoration planning be preceded by a structured decision tool to minimize risk of failure and to ensure resources are allocated to sites with the highest ecological and social return on investment.

In Seychelles, the Restoration Site Suitability Key is being developed as part of this protocol to provide a standardized screening process for future restoration interventions. The tool is designed as a sequential yes/no evaluation that guides managers through critical ecological, physical, and governance criteria before site approval. While not mandatory at present, its adoption will strengthen national practice by aligning restoration planning with the relevant principles of the Ten Golden Rules for Seagrass Restoration²⁹ and UNEP/WIOMSA guidelines.

Evidence of historical and current distribution ensures that restoration is attempted only where seagrasses naturally occurred. **This reflects the principle that protecting and recovering existing meadows must remain the first priority, as restoration outside natural ranges has low success probability and diverts resources from conservation.**

Connectivity to donor meadows is included to ensure recruitment potential and genetic diversity. This reflects the rule of selecting appropriate sites and contributes to broader seascape resilience by reconnecting fragmented meadows.

Reversal of stressors (e.g., pollution, dredging, anchoring) is a central criterion. This is consistent with the principle that root causes of decline must be tackled first, as planting into degraded environments without mitigation will not be successful.

Environmental thresholds, substrate and hydrodynamic suitability (salinity, water quality, storm exposure, depth, tidal regime, sediment stability, and light availability) are included to ensure that projects are grounded in realistic, ecologically informed goals, respecting the tolerance limits of target species.

Legal and human-use constraints ensure that proposed interventions align with governance frameworks, marine spatial planning, and local community use. This reflects the principle of working inclusively with stakeholders, embedding restoration in the broader social-ecological system.

By embedding this decision process in a Standardized National Protocol, restoration activities become consistent across agencies and NGOs, reducing ad hoc or opportunistic planting. It also creates a defensible approval framework for government and donors, ensuring that interventions are ecologically justified, cost-effective, and scalable.

²⁹ Unsworth, R.K.F., Jones, B.L.H., Bertelli, C.M., Coals, L., Cullen-Unsworth, L.C., Mendzil, A.F., Rees, S.C., Taylor, F., Walter, B., Evans, A.J., 2025. Ten golden rules for restoration to secure resilient and just seagrass social-ecological systems. *Plants People Planet* 7, 33–48. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ppp3.10560>

Step	Criteria	Answer	Next Action / Outcome	Mitigation
1	Historical presence			
	Was seagrass historically present (aerial photos, maps, datasets, literature available, local ecological/cultural knowledge)?	No	NOT SUITABLE - DO NOT PLANT	
		Yes	Go to Step 2	Go to Step 2
2	Current evidence			
	Is there evidence of current or recent seagrass presence?	No	Unsuitable (Mitigation Required)	Conduct spot check at site using monitoring protocol
		Yes	Go to Step 3	Go to Step 3
3	Natural recruitment			
	Is the site close (5 km) to natural donor meadows (source of vegetative fragments)?	No	NOT SUITABLE - DO NOT PLANT	
		Yes	Go to Step 4	
4	Stressor/ Local threat			
	Has the cause of seagrass decline (pollution, dredging, anchoring, etc.) been addressed?	No	Unsuitable (Mitigation Required)	Restoration not advised / Do not Plant until stressor is mitigated.
		Yes	Go to Step 5	Go to Step 5
5	Previous success			
	Has restoration been previously attempted successfully in similar conditions?	No	Unsuitable (Mitigation Required)	Only experimental pilot (10*10 m max) should be trialled
		Yes	Go to Step 6	Go to Step 6
6	Substrate suitability			
	Is sediment composition and depth suitable for selected species (\geq 80 cm for <i>Enhalus</i> ; sandy/muddy mix for <i>Thalassia</i>)?	No	NOT SUITABLE - DO NOT PLANT	
		Yes	Go to Step 7	
7	Sediment stability			
	Is the site free from significant erosion or burial risk?	No	Unsuitable (Mitigation Required)	Stabilization measures needed first. Costly.
		Yes	Go to Step 8	Go to Step 8
8	Bioturbation			
	Is bioturbation (e.g. polychaete, stingrays) within tolerable limits?	No	Unsuitable (Mitigation Required)	Only experimental pilot (10*10 m max) should be trialled
		Yes	Go to Step 9	Go to Step 9

Step	Criteria	Answer	Next Action / Outcome	Mitigation
9	Depth & tidal regime			
	Are depth and tidal exposure similar to nearby natural seagrass beds?	No Yes	NOT SUITABLE - DO NOT PLANT Go to Step 10	
10	Light availability			
	Is underwater light > minimum requirement (10–20% surface irradiance, species-specific)?	No Yes	NOT SUITABLE - DO NOT PLANT Go to Step 11	
11	Water quality			
	Are turbidity, nutrients, pollutants, and epiphyte load within acceptable thresholds?	No Yes	NOT SUITABLE - DO NOT PLANT Go to Step 12	
12	Salinity & temperature			
	Are salinity and temperature within species tolerance ranges?	No Yes	NOT SUITABLE - DO NOT PLANT Go to Step 13	
13	Wave & storm exposure			
	Is exposure below tolerance limits of target species?	No Yes	Unsuitable (Mitigation Required) Go to Step 14	stabilization or breakwater/nature-based protection required first.
14	Tidal elevation			
	Is risk of desiccation during low tide exposure minimal?	No Yes	NOT SUITABLE - DO NOT PLANT Go to Step 15	
15	Legal permissions secured?			
	Are legal permits and management approvals secured?	No Yes	Unsuitable (Mitigation Required) Go to Step 16	Contact Management Authority and GoS -Ministry of Environment
16	Human			
	Are there no major constraints (structures, dredged channels, high-traffic zones)?	No Yes	NOT SUITABLE - DO NOT PLANT SITE SUITABLE for restoration	

RESTORATION GUIDELINES

The restoration guidelines proposed for Seychelles are designed to align national practice with international standards while addressing the ecological characteristics of the Western Indian Ocean (WIO). Core activities, including donor site selection, low-impact harvesting, transplantation techniques, and adaptive monitoring, follow the UNEP–Nairobi Convention/WIOMSA guidelines. These approaches are consistent with global best practice, where restoration is implemented only after stressors are reversed, suitable donor meadows identified, and site-level feasibility confirmed¹¹.

In Seychelles, restoration efforts should prioritize persistent seagrass species such as *Enhalus acoroides*, *Thalassia hemprichii* and *Thalassodendron ciliatum* which provide high structural stability and long-term ecosystem services but are less resilient to disturbance and slow to recover naturally. Empirical studies demonstrate that *Enhalus* requires deep, stable sediments (>80 cm) for anchorage, and transplant success declines markedly under high turbidity or sediment erosion³⁰. Similarly, seed-based restoration trials have shown that germination and seedling survival are strongly influenced by burial depth and protection from predation or bioturbation, with optimal establishment achieved when seeds are shallow-buried and protected with mesh bags³¹. These findings emphasize the importance of integrating sediment characteristics, hydrodynamics, and propagule handling techniques into the national framework.

Opportunistic species, such as *Syringodium isoetifolium* can also play an important role in restoration. It is noteworthy that this species has been recorded fruiting and flowering more than any other seagrass species in Seychelles (Mortimer, Gendron, Barret, unpublished data). The possible role of this species in restoration warrants further assessment.

The Seychelles guidelines also adopt a phased and modular approach to restoration, beginning with small-scale pilot plots (~10 × 10 m), progressing through clustered transplantation, and only scaling up once survival thresholds (>50–60% after two to three months) are achieved. This mirrors best practice recommendations from the WIO and other regions, where gradual scaling reduces donor pressure and ensures adaptive learning from early trials. Post-restoration monitoring shall track indicators such as Percentage cover, species composition and canopy height, and epiphyte load, following the national Seychelles protocol methodologies.

³⁰ Shen, J., Yin, L., Zhang, J., Jia, S., Wang, Y., Wang, D., Cai, Z., Chen, S., 2023. Restoration performance of *Thalassia hemprichii* and *Enhalus acoroides* at Gaolong bay and Xincun lagoon, Hainan Island, China. *Front. Mar. Sci.* 10, 1294779. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmars.2023.1294779>

³¹ Yu, S., et al. (2019). Preliminary study on seed-based restoration for *Enhalus acoroides* meadow. *Journal of Tropical Oceanography*, 38(1), 49–54

Activity	#	Details/Best practices
1. Donor-Site Selection and Harvest		
Restoration Site Suitability Key	1.0	Use the Restoration Suitability Key to verify your future restoration interventions
Identify a Healthy Donor Meadow	1.1	Choose a nearby meadow with robust seagrass stands (good shoot density, high leaf biomass, limited signs of stress).
	1.2	Where possible, use areas where plants have naturally been dislodged (e.g. storm or wave-disturbed edges) to reduce damage to intact meadows.
Mark Low-Impact Harvest Zones	1.3	Subdivide the donor meadow into grids or zones to spread out the harvest so that no single area is overexploited.
	1.4	Limit harvest to a small percentage of each grid (e.g. 10–15 %) to minimize ecological damage.
	1.5	Inspect seagrass plant for flower or fruit.
Best Seasonal Window	1.6	Plan rhizome collection outside peak flowering/fruited periods to protect reproductive capacity.
	1.7	Schedule during neap tides or calmer conditions, reducing stress and logistical challenges.
2. Rhizome Harvest Techniques		
Manual Extraction	2.1	A cylindrical coring device (e.g., a PVC sewer pipe, length 50cm, diameter minimum of 20 cm) will be used to extract seagrass plugs from a donor seagrass bed. The device will be pushed into the sediment to obtain a core plug containing seagrass shoots, rhizomes, and sediment (Figure 7).
	2.2	Target segments with multiple shoots (3–5) and an intact root bundle, ensuring at least ~10–15 cm of rhizome length.
On-Site Washing	2.3	Gently rinse excess sediment from rhizomes plug to facilitate transport.
	2.4	Avoid freshwater rinses, which can cause osmotic shock. Instead, use ambient seawater in buckets or bins.
Transport & Storage	2.5	Keep plugs submerged in aerated seawater to maintain oxygen levels.
	2.6	If transport exceeds a few hours, maintain cool conditions (e.g. shade or insulated containers) to reduce metabolic stress.
3. Pre-Planting Preparation		
Quality Check	3.1	Discard rhizomes with significant damage or decayed root tissue.
	3.2	Prioritize shoots with bright green leaves (indicating active growth) and robust root networks.
Trim Excess Leaves	3.3	Optionally trim the leaf tips (removing ~25–30 % of blade length) to reduce transpiration stress and help the transplant re-establish, while ensuring enough blade length remains for photosynthesis.

Figure 7. The plug method utilises tubes as coring devices to extract the plants with the sediment and rhizomes intact.

Activity	#	Details/Best practices
4. Transplant Deployment		
Restoration Site Preparation	4.1	Mark out the pilot restoration grid 10*10 m using surface buoys or anchored stakes, ensuring planned spacing (1–2 m between transplants).
	4.2	If necessary, deploy biodegradable mats (e.g. natural fibre gunny bag) to stabilize very loose sediment.
Planting Depth and Method	4.3	The extracted seagrass plug will then be transplanted into a recipient site by inserting it into a hole of approximately 50 cm in depth, created using the same coring device. This method ensures minimal disturbance to the seagrass structure while maintaining sediment integrity, promoting successful transplantation and seagrass bed restoration.
	4.4	Gently press or excavate the sediment to create a trench. Lay the rhizome horizontally so that roots are well covered, leaving only the leaf shoots above the substrate.
	4.5	In dynamic or higher-energy areas, secure plug and rhizomes by pegging them down with biodegradable stakes or with small stone anchors until they root naturally.
Spacing Strategy	4.6	Plant in clusters, each with a small group of spaced ~30–50 cm apart within the cluster.
	4.7	Clusters are spaced 1–2 m apart, creating “patches” that can expand and coalesce over time.
	4.8	This modular approach also helps you vary density in different subplots, enabling adaptive trials (i.e. higher density vs. lower density).
Minimize Disturbance	4.9	Work systematically up-current to avoid re-suspending silt onto newly transplanted areas.
	4.10	Limit foot traffic or diver movement, especially in fine silty sediments that become easily turbid.
5. Post-Transplant Care		
Immediate Stability Check	5.1	Gently tug on planted rhizomes to ensure they’re well anchored.
	5.2	Inspect for sediment collapse or excessive turbidity, re-bury if rhizome is exposed.
Monitoring Schedule	5.3	In the first month, conduct weekly to biweekly checks for signs of uprooting, burial, or algal overgrowth. Re-bury dislodged rhizomes promptly.
	5.4	Record shoot survival and leaf condition; successful plants often show new leaf growth or fresh root elongation after ~4–6 weeks.
6. Adaptive Management and Scaling Up		
Evaluate Survival Rates after 2 Months	6.1	Aim for an early survival threshold of ~50–60%.
	6.2	If below target, identify issues (e.g. wave stress, insufficient burial depth) and adjust methods.
Supplementary Planting	6.3	Fill gaps or expand clusters if the initial planting remains stable after 3–6 months.
	6.4	Incorporate seed-based restoration once rhizome clusters are established; seeds are more likely to recruit successfully in calmer microhabitats created by mature rhizomes.
Longer-Term Maintenance	6.5	Monitor canopy development: new leaf production, rhizome extension, coverage using monitoring protocol (See Annex 2)
	6.6	Watch for nutrient pollution, siltation, or disease. Undertake water quality monitoring at restoration location (See Annex 3)
Scaling	6.7	Once pilot areas show stable survival and early expansion (usually after ~12 months), replicate or upscale intervention.

Data Management

Effective data management is central to ensuring that seagrass monitoring and restoration activities in Seychelles produce credible, comparable, and policy-relevant outputs. This protocol establishes a national framework for data governance, harmonized with Seagrass-Watch and SeagrassNet standards, while aligning with international commitments on biodiversity observation and open data (Duffy et al., 2019; McKenzie et al., 2003; Short et al., 2015).

NATIONAL FOCAL POINT

The Government of Seychelles shall designate a national focal point i.e. a competent authority or unit within government responsible for:

- Coordinating the receipt of all seagrass monitoring and restoration data.
- Conducting quality assurance (QA) and quality control (QC) checks on submitted datasets.
- Maintaining the official national repository of seagrass data.
- Facilitating data sharing with regional and global initiatives (e.g., GCRMN, GOOS/MBON, Seagrass-Watch, OBIS).

During consultations, stakeholders raised whether the Seychelles Marine Spatial Plan (SMSP) could serve as the national focal point for data coordination, given its 10-year revision cycle, which already aligns with Seychelles' international reporting obligations.

Quality Assurance / Quality Control Procedures

The national focal point shall apply a two-tiered QA/QC process for the received dataset:

Validation: checking completeness of datasheets, consistency of metadata, and compliance with coding and file naming conventions.

Verification: assessing species identifications, cover estimates, and photoquadrats against reference guides (e.g., Seagrass-Watch ID sheets, global cover guides).

Datasets that fail QA/QC shall be returned to the data provider with corrective feedback.

Data Format Requirements

All submissions shall include:

- Datasheets completed in Excel format (.xlsx), using the standardised templates provided in Annexes of this protocol.
- Photographic records, including all quadrat and transect images.

No dataset will be considered complete without both components.

Photoquadrat Naming Convention

All photoquadrats must be named following this standard format:

yyyymmdd_REGIONCODE_LOCATIONCODE_SITECODE_TRANSECTNUMBER_QUADRATNUMBE

Example: 20250715_MAH_VOLBERT_S01_T01_Q03

This format ensures chronological order, spatial traceability, and facilitates automated data processing and archiving.

DATA ACCESS AND LICENSING FOR RESTRICTED DATASETS

Seagrass monitoring datasets may contain restricted or sensitive information (e.g., unpublished research data, proprietary survey results, or information linked to private or project-funded studies). To ensure transparency while maintaining confidentiality, a two-tier licensing approach shall apply:

1. Metadata: Open Access (CC BY 4.0)

All datasets included in the National Seagrass Monitoring Framework must be accompanied by a public metadata record to ensure discoverability, citation, and integration into national and global repositories (e.g., OBIS, GOOS, SeagrassSpotter).

Metadata shall be licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International (CC BY 4.0) license ³², which allows others to share and reuse the metadata with proper credit to the original creator.

2. Data: Controlled or Restricted Access

When the underlying data are not publicly available, access should be managed through a data request and approval process overseen by the designated national coordinating entity (to be confirmed).

Data providers may choose to:

- Share data upon formal request and approval through a Data Use Agreement; or
- Publish summary-level or aggregated data products while retaining ownership of raw datasets.

Recommended data access statement should include “The dataset described by this metadata record is not publicly available. Access may be granted for non-commercial research, management, or reporting purposes upon request to the data custodian, subject to a data use agreement.”

FAIR Data Principles

All national seagrass datasets shall adhere to the FAIR principles.

Findable: Each dataset and photograph must be stored with unique identifiers (e.g., codes, filenames, metadata records) to ensure traceability

Accessible: Data shall be deposited in a secure, government-managed repository and made available to partners, with appropriate levels of access.

Interoperable: Standardised codes, formats (Excel, CSV), and metadata structures will be used to ensure compatibility across agencies and with international platforms.

Reusable: Comprehensive metadata (e.g., site descriptors, species lists, habitat conditions, sampling methods) must accompany each dataset, enabling long-term scientific reuse.

³² Creative Commons. (2024).. Retrieved from <https://creativecommons.org/>

This approach ensures Seychelles' seagrass monitoring data are not only protected and centrally managed, but also comparable and useful to both national decision-makers and international scientific communities.

INTEGRATION WITH GLOBAL AND OPEN-ACCESS SYSTEMS

The Seychelles seagrass monitoring and data-management framework proposed is designed to support national reporting needs while generating the evidence required for application of the IUCN Red List of Ecosystems (RLE) at national scale. Consistent with guidance on integrating monitoring outcomes into RLE assessments for connected coastal wetlands³³, the protocol generates time-series and spatially explicit data on ecosystem distribution, condition, and pressures that can be directly mapped to RLE criteria (notably Criteria A–D), including changes in extent, degradation of biotic processes, and exposure to drivers of decline. Validated datasets should be systematically shared with Ocean Biodiversity Information System (OBIS) through periodic submission of species occurrence records, georeferenced monitoring sites, and associated environmental metadata, ensuring Seychelles contributes to the global biodiversity knowledge base. In parallel, alignment with Global Ocean Observing System (GOOS) and its Marine Biodiversity Observation Network (MBON) ensures that core indicators, such as seagrass canopy cover, species composition, and spatial extent, are consistent with Essential Ocean Variables (EOVs), thereby supporting international climate, biodiversity, and ecosystem-risk reporting. By embedding RLE-relevant indicators within open and interoperable data systems, Seychelles ensures that seagrass monitoring outputs are robust for national decision-making, comparable at regional scales, and discoverable globally, while remaining directly usable for future national IUCN Red List of Ecosystems assessments.

³³ Bland, L. M., et al. (2020). Integrating outcomes of IUCN Red List of Ecosystems assessments for connected coastal wetlands. *Conservation Letters*.

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1. FIELD PROCEDURE – CORE INDICATORS(REQUIRED)

A – TRANSECT PLACEMENT

1. Place or Locate the permanent marker for the site (origin point of the transect).
2. Start GPS tracking and take a picture of GPS date and time
3. Set the compass bearing:
 - Use a bearing perpendicular to the shoreline, oriented from shallow to deeper water.
 - Read the compass accurately and record the bearing on the data sheet.
4. Lay out the 50 m transect line along the recorded compass bearing. Ensure the tape is taut and follows a straight line.

B - RECORD TRANSECT METADATA

At the beginning of the transect, Record:

- | | |
|--|--|
| 5. Site code | 10. GPS coordinates at the end (50 m) - In
Decimal Degrees to 5 decimal places
(e.g. -4.12345, 45.12345) |
| 6. Transect number | |
| 7. Observer names and organisations (full
name + surname) | 11. Compass bearing used. |
| 8. Date | 12. Take a picture of the slate |
| 9. GPS coordinates at the start (0 m) – In
Decimal Degrees to 5 decimal places
(e.g. -4.12345, 45.12345) | |

C - QUADRAT PLACEMENT AND MEASUREMENT

13. Quadrats are placed on the right side of the transect line.
14. **Place 11 quadrats at 5 m intervals:** 0 m, 5 m, 10 m, ... 50 m
15. Always start at 0 m to maintain consistent sampling.

At each quadrat:

16. **Photograph** the quadrat
 - Take the picture before any disturbance.
 - Ensure the quadrat edges are fully visible.
 - Use the photo label board showing site, transect, and station number.

Record:

17. Estimate and record total seagrass plant cover (%).
18. Identify all seagrass species in the quadrat according to the technical skills of your field team.
19. Estimate the total percentage cover (%) of each seagrass species (or seagrass morphotype), based on its total area within the quadrat.
20. Ensure that the sum of species-specific seagrass covers equals the total seagrass plant cover (%).
21. Estimate and record total percentage cover of Macroalgae
22. Estimate and record total percentage cover of any other category

D - SECOND TRANSECT

23. From the permanent marker, measure 25 m to the left.
24. Mark the starting point and lay the transect using the same compass bearing as Transect 1.
25. Repeat all procedures from Sections B to C

E-THIRD TRANSECT

26. From the permanent marker, measure 25 m to the right.
27. Lay the transect along the same compass bearing.
28. Repeat all procedures from Sections B to C

2. PROPOSED LIST OF REGION AND LOCATION

SMSP Zone/ Type	Region	Region Code	Location	Location Code	Seagrass Extent (Ha)	Total Extent (Ha)
Marine National Park (Pre-SMSP)	Baie Ternay Marine National Park	BTMNP	Cap Ternay Bay	CTB	12.7	87.1
Marine National Park (Pre-SMSP)	Saint Anne Marine National Park	SAMNP	TBD		125.9	965.5
Marine National Park (Pre-SMSP)	Port Launay Marine National Park	PLMNP	Port Launay Bay	PLB	12.5	163.3
Marine National Park (Pre-SMSP)	Curieuse Marine National Park	CMNP	Curieuse	CUR	36.1	1341.1
Marine National Park (Pre-SMSP)	Ile Cocos, Ile La Fouche, Ilot Platte	ICILFIP	Coco Island	COCO	0.0	85.6
Marine National Park (Pre-SMSP)	Silhouette Island Marine National Park	SIMNP	Silhouette Island	SIL	0.0	2131.8
Shell Reserve	Mahe (Anse Faure-Fairy Land) Shell Reserve	MAFFLSR	Anse aux Pins	AAP	74.1	334.5
Shell Reserve	La Digue Shell Reserve	LDSR	La Digue	DIGUE	4.0	158.0
Special Reserve (Pre-SMSP)	Aldabra (Marine) Special Reserve	AMSR	Aldabra	ALDA	3494.9	255900.0
Special Reserve (Pre-SMSP)	Aride Island Special Nature Reserve	AISNR	Aride Island	ARID	0.0	720.0
Special Reserve (Pre-SMSP)	Cousin Special Nature Reserve	CSNR	TBD (no extensive seagrass at Cousin)		0.0	28.9
Zone 1 (SMSP)	Amirantes South (Marine) National Park	ASMNP	Marie-Louise	MARIL	9299.1	133400.0
Zone 1 (SMSP)	Bird Island (Ile aux Vaches) (Marine) National Park	BIMNP	Bird Island	BIRD	585.2	10500.0
Zone 1 (SMSP)	D'Arros Atoll (Marine) National Park	DAAMNP	D'Arros	DARR	78.9	2340.0
Zone 1 (SMSP)	D'Arros to Poivre Atolls (Marine) National Park	DAPAMNP	TBD (no Island)		1238.4	37000.0
Zone 1 (SMSP)	Aldabra Group (Marine) National Park	AGMNP	Assomption Island	ASSO	148.7	15900.0
Zone 1 (SMSP)	Aldabra Group (Marine) National Park	AGMNP	Other		0.0	20106500.0
Zone 2 (SMSP)	Desroches Atoll (Marine) Sustainable Use Area	DAMSUA	Desroches Island	DESR	8021.1	32900.0
Zone 2 (SMSP)	Poivre Atoll (Marine) Sustainable Use Area	PAMSUA	Poivre Island	POIV	781.0	5400.0
Zone 2 (SMSP)	Amirantes to Fortune Bank (Marine) Sustainable Use Area	AFBMSUA	St Joseph	STJO	916.1	7360.0
Zone 2 (SMSP)	Alphonse Group (Marine) Sustainable Use Area	AGMSUA	Alphonse, Bijoutier and St Francois		2440.8	21300.0
Zone 2 (SMSP)	Farquhar Atoll Sustainable Use Area	FASUA	Farquhar Island	FARQ	3492.6	40800.0
Zone 2 (SMSP)	Amirantes to Fortune Bank (Marine) Sustainable Use Area	AFBMSUA	Remire to African Banks	REM	6430.9	132500.0
Zone 2 (SMSP)	Amirantes to Fortune Bank (Marine) Sustainable Use Area	AFBMSUA	Ile Platte	ILEP	11260.4	237700.0
Zone 2 (SMSP)	Denis Island (Marine) Sustainable Use Area	DIMSUA	Denis Island		96.1	2960.0
Zone 2 (SMSP)	Farquhar Archipelago Sustainable Use Area	FASUA	Providence, Cerf and Saint-Pierre		20477.0	1447800.0
Zone 2 (SMSP)	Cosmoledo and Astove Archipelago Sustainable Use Area	CAASUA	Cosmoledo		5799.6	531000.0
Zone 2 (SMSP)	Amirantes to Fortune Bank (Marine) Sustainable Use Area	AFBMSUA	Coetivy		2379.7	295000.0
Zone 2 (SMSP)	Amirantes to Fortune Bank (Marine) Sustainable Use Area	AFBMSUA	Other		81083.5	21085140.0
Zone 2 (SMSP)	Cosmoledo and Astove Archipelago Sustainable Use Area	CAASUA	Astove		379.7	531000.0
Zone 3 (SMSP)	Inner Islands Multiple Use Area	PRA	Baie Ste Anne, Praslin		170.7	411.0
Zone 3 (SMSP)	Inner Islands Multiple Use Area	PRA	Cote D'Or, Praslin		30.1	327.5
Zone 3 (SMSP)	Inner Islands Multiple Use Area	MPII	TBD: e.g.: Grand Anse/ Consolation/ Beauvallon Bay		413.2	

4. BENTHIC CATEGORY

category	sediment_type	scientific_name	scientific_name2	Note
Abiotic	Mud			smooth, sticky
Abiotic	Fine Sand			smooth, slight roughness
Abiotic	Sand			rough grainy texture, distinguishable particles.
Abiotic	Coarse Sand			coarse, loose particles include coral rubble
Abiotic	Gravel			very coarse with small stones include coral rubble
Macroalgae				
Hard coral				
Seagrass species		<i>Enhalus</i>	<i>acoroides</i>	Gomon zerb gran fey
Seagrass species		<i>Thalassodendron</i>	<i>ciliatum</i>	Gomon zerb levantay
Seagrass species		<i>Syringodium</i>	<i>isoetifolium</i>	Gomon zerb spageti
Seagrass species		<i>Ruppia</i>	<i>maritima</i>	Gomon zerb sed
Seagrass species		<i>Thalassia</i>	<i>hemprichii</i>	Gomon zerb torti
Seagrass species		<i>Oceana</i>	<i>serrulata</i>	Gomon zerb torti
Seagrass species		<i>Cymodocea</i>	<i>rotundata</i>	Gomon zerb torti
Seagrass species		<i>Halodule</i>	<i>uninervis</i>	Gomon zerb torti
Seagrass species		<i>Halophila</i>	<i>decipiens</i>	Gomon zerb pti fey oval
Seagrass species		<i>Halophila</i>	<i>stipulacea</i>	Gomon zerb zorey lapen
Seagrass species		<i>Halophila</i>	<i>ovalis (complex)</i>	Gomon zerb papiyon
Seagrass morphotype			Flat strap like leaves + Long leaves	Gomon zerb gran fey
Seagrass morphotype			Fan-Like Leaves	Gomon zerb levantay
Seagrass morphotype			Flat strap like leaves	Gomon zerb torti
Seagrass morphotype			Spaghetti like leaves	Gomon zerb spageti
Seagrass morphotype			Oval and in pairs leaves	Gomon zerb zorey lapen
Other mobile fauna				
Unknown				
Other				

Coral rubble should be included under the Abiotic category and is defined as mechanically or chemically abraded fragments of reef-building organisms or reef rock that are larger than the sand fraction; its presence should be specified in the Notes or cover sample notes field of the datasheet. Example: in Sediment type = Gravel + Note/Cover Sample= Coral Rubble

5. DATA ENTRY SPREAD SHEET

Available here: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18772492>

This spreadsheet is the standardised data-entry and reference framework for seagrass monitoring in Seychelles and it shall be used by all participating organisations. It defines common structures, controlled vocabularies, and metadata required to ensure consistent data recording, validation, and integration across sites and monitoring programmes.

The spreadsheet has been adapted and modified from the MarineGEO Seagrass Habitat Monitoring Protocol³⁴ to align with the Seychelles national context, SMSP zoning, and locally relevant seagrass and benthic classifications.

It supports standardised data entry, quality control, and interoperability with national and international seagrass monitoring frameworks.

34 MarineGEO (2025). MarineGEO Seagrass Habitat Monitoring Protocol. Smithsonian Institution. <https://doi.org/10.25573/serc.14925114>

6. PRIORITY AREAS FOR SENTINEL SITE MONITORING IMPLEMENTATION

Methodology

This prioritization is designed to balance ecological importance, spatial representativity, and operational feasibility, while remaining aligned Seychelles Marine Spatial Planning.

A core principle is to ensure representative coverage of both Inner Islands and Outer Islands, recognising their contrasting ecological settings, pressures, accessibility, and management contexts. Inner Island seagrass meadows are typically subject to higher anthropogenic pressures (coastal development, tourism, land-based runoff), while Outer Island systems are generally more remote, less disturbed, and critical for capturing baseline and reference conditions at national scale. Both contexts are essential to accurately characterise national seagrass status, trends, and risks.

Spatial Framework and Regional Units

The spatial unit for prioritisation is the SMSP Region, as defined in the Seychelles Marine Spatial Plan (SMSP). These regions provide a nationally endorsed, policy-relevant framework that integrates ecological, governance, and management considerations. All seagrass extent estimates are spatially intersected with SMSP regional polygons to ensure consistency with national planning instruments.

Scenario-Based Prioritisation

Three complementary prioritisation scenarios are applied in parallel. Each scenario generates a ranked list of regions, which are subsequently combined to identify priority regions and locations.

Scenario 1: Absolute Seagrass Extent (Area-Based Importance)

Regions are ranked according to the total estimated seagrass extent (hectares) within each SMSP region, using the national seagrass mapping produced by Rowlands et al. 2024. Regions with larger absolute seagrass area represent a higher proportion of national natural capital, carbon storage, and ecosystem service provision. Prioritising these regions ensures that monitoring captures the majority of Seychelles' seagrass resource and maximises national relevance.

Scenario 2: Relative Seagrass Importance within Regions (Density-Based Importance)

For each SMSP region, a relative seagrass coverage index (%) is calculated by dividing total seagrass extent by the total area of the regional polygon:

$$\text{Relative Seagrass Coverage (\%)} = \text{Seagrass Extent (ha)} / \text{Region Area (ha)} \times 100$$

This scenario highlights regions where seagrass forms a dominant or structurally important habitat relative to regional size, even if absolute area is moderate. Such regions may be ecologically sensitive, highly dependent on seagrass functions, or more vulnerable to proportional habitat loss.

Scenario 3: Implementation Feasibility and Existing Capacity

Regions are designated based on realistic implementation potential, informed by stakeholder consultation and existing institutional arrangements. Criteria include:

- Confirmed local or institutional monitoring capacity
- Presence of existing monitoring frameworks and dive station (e.g. MPAs, SPGA, NGO-led programmes, research stations)
- Logistical accessibility and cost-efficiency

This scenario ensures that early phases of national monitoring are feasible, sustainable, and likely to deliver high-quality data. It also supports integration with existing efforts rather than duplication.

Scenario 1: Absolute Seagrass Extent

Rank	SMSP Zone/ Type	Region	Location	Seagrass Extent (Km ²)
1	Zone 2 (SMSP)	Amirantes to Fortune Bank (Marine) Sustainable Use Area	Other	810.84
2	Zone 2 (SMSP)	Farquhar Archipelago Sustainable Use Area	Providence, Cerf and Saint-Pierre	204.77
3	Zone 2 (SMSP)	Amirantes to Fortune Bank (Marine) Sustainable Use Area	Ile Platte	112.60
4	Zone 1 (SMSP)	Amirantes South (Marine) National Park	Marie-Louise	92.99
5	Zone 2 (SMSP)	Desroches Atoll (Marine) Sustainable Use Area	Desroches Island	80.21
6	Zone 2 (SMSP)	Amirantes to Fortune Bank (Marine) Sustainable Use Area	Remire to African Banks	64.31
7	Zone 2 (SMSP)	Cosmoledo and Astove Archipelago Sustainable Use Area	Cosmoledo	58.00
8	Special Reserve (Pre-SMSP)	Aldabra (Marine) Special Reserve	Aldabra	34.95
9	Zone 2 (SMSP)	Farquhar Atoll Sustainable Use Area	Farquhar Island	34.93
10	Zone 2 (SMSP)	Alphonse Group (Marine) Sustainable Use Area	Alphonse, Bijoutier and St Francois	24.41
11	Zone 2 (SMSP)	Amirantes to Fortune Bank (Marine) Sustainable Use Area	Coetivy	23.80
12	Zone 1 (SMSP)	D'Arros to Poivre Atolls (Marine) National Park	TBD (no Island)	12.38
13	Zone 2 (SMSP)	Amirantes to Fortune Bank (Marine) Sustainable Use Area	St Joseph	9.16
14	Zone 2 (SMSP)	Poivre Atoll (Marine) Sustainable Use Area	Poivre Island	7.81
15	Zone 1 (SMSP)	Bird Island (Ile aux Vaches) (Marine) National Park	Bird Island	5.85
16	Zone 3 (SMSP)	Inner Islands Multiple Use Area	TBD, Mahe Plateau Inner Island	4.13
17	Zone 2 (SMSP)	Cosmoledo and Astove Archipelago Sustainable Use Area	Astove	3.80
18	Zone 3 (SMSP)	Inner Islands Multiple Use Area	Baie Ste Anne, Praslin	1.71
19	Zone 1 (SMSP)	Aldabra Group (Marine) National Park	Assomption Island	1.49
20	Marine National Park (Pre-SMSP)	Saint Anne Marine National Park	TBD	1.26
21	Zone 2 (SMSP)	Denis Island (Marine) Sustainable Use Area	Denis Island	0.96
22	Zone 1 (SMSP)	D'Arros Atoll (Marine) National Park	D'Arros	0.79
23	Shell Reserve	Mahe (Anse Faure-Fairy Land) Shell Reserve	Anse aux Pins	0.74
24	Marine National Park (Pre-SMSP)	Curieuse Marine National Park	Curieuse	0.36
25	Zone 3 (SMSP)	Inner Islands Multiple Use Area	Cote D'Or, Praslin	0.30
26	Marine National Park (Pre-SMSP)	Baie Ternay Marine National Park	Cap Ternay Bay	0.13
27	Marine National Park (Pre-SMSP)	Port Launay Marine National Park	Port Launay Bay	0.13
28	Shell Reserve	La Digue Shell Reserve	La Digue	0.04
33	Zone 1 (SMSP)	Aldabra Group (Marine) National Park	Other	TBD
30	Marine National Park (Pre-SMSP)	Silhouette Island Marine National Park	Silhouette Island	TBD
31	Special Reserve (Pre-SMSP)	Aride Island Special Nature Reserve	Aride Island	TBD
29	Marine National Park (Pre-SMSP)	Ile Cocos, Ile La Fouche, Ilot Platte	Coco Island	TBD
32	Special Reserve (Pre-SMSP)	Cousin Special Nature Reserve	TBD (no extensive seagrass at Cousin)	TBD
TB D	Zone 3 (SMSP)	Inner Islands Multiple Use Area	Beauvallon Bay, Mahe	TBD
TB D	Zone 3 (SMSP)	Inner Islands Multiple Use Area	Anse La Mouche, Mahe	TBD
TB D	Zone 3 (SMSP)	Inner Islands Multiple Use Area	Grand Anse, Praslin	TBD
TB D	Zone 3 (SMSP)	Inner Islands Multiple Use Area	Consolation, Praslin	TBD

Scenario 2. Relative Seagrass Coverage

Rank	SMSP Zone/ Type	Region	Location	% Seagrass
1	Zone 3 (SMSP)	Inner Islands Multiple Use Area	Baie Ste Anne, Praslin	41.54
2	Zone 2 (SMSP)	Desroches Atoll (Marine) Sustainable Use Area	Desroches Island	24.38
3	Shell Reserve	Mahe (Anse Faure-Fairy Land) Shell Reserve	Anse aux Pins	22.17
4	Marine National Park (Pre-SMSP)	Baie Ternay Marine National Park	Cap Ternay Bay	14.58
5	Zone 2 (SMSP)	Poivre Atoll (Marine) Sustainable Use Area	Poivre Island	14.46
6	Marine National Park (Pre-SMSP)	Saint Anne Marine National Park	TBD	13.04
7	Zone 2 (SMSP)	Amirantes to Fortune Bank (Marine) Sustainable Use Area	St Joseph	12.45
8	Zone 2 (SMSP)	Alphonse Group (Marine) Sustainable Use Area	Alphonse, Bijoutier and St Francois	11.46
9	Zone 3 (SMSP)	Inner Islands Multiple Use Area	Cote D'Or, Praslin	9.18
10	Zone 2 (SMSP)	Farquhar Atoll Sustainable Use Area	Farquhar Island	8.56
11	Marine National Park (Pre-SMSP)	Port Launay Marine National Park	Port Launay Bay	7.68
12	Zone 1 (SMSP)	Amirantes South (Marine) National Park	Marie-Louise	6.97
13	Zone 1 (SMSP)	Bird Island (Ile aux Vaches) (Marine) National Park	Bird Island	5.57
14	Zone 2 (SMSP)	Amirantes to Fortune Bank (Marine) Sustainable Use Area	Remire to African Banks	4.85
15	Zone 2 (SMSP)	Amirantes to Fortune Bank (Marine) Sustainable Use Area	Ile Platte	4.74
16	Zone 1 (SMSP)	D'Arros Atoll (Marine) National Park	D'Arros	3.37
17	Zone 1 (SMSP)	D'Arros to Poivre Atolls (Marine) National Park	TBD (no Island)	3.35
18	Zone 2 (SMSP)	Denis Island (Marine) Sustainable Use Area	Denis Island	3.25
19	Marine National Park (Pre-SMSP)	Curieuse Marine National Park	Curieuse	2.69
20	Shell Reserve	La Digue Shell Reserve	La Digue	2.53
21	Zone 2 (SMSP)	Farquhar Archipelago Sustainable Use Area	Providence, Cerf and Saint-Pierre	1.41
22	Special Reserve (Pre-SMSP)	Aldabra (Marine) Special Reserve	Aldabra	1.37
23	Zone 2 (SMSP)	Cosmoledo and Astove Archipelago Sustainable Use Area	Cosmoledo	1.09
24	Zone 1 (SMSP)	Aldabra Group (Marine) National Park	Assomption Island	0.94
25	Zone 2 (SMSP)	Amirantes to Fortune Bank (Marine) Sustainable Use Area	Coetivy	0.81
26	Zone 2 (SMSP)	Amirantes to Fortune Bank (Marine) Sustainable Use Area	Other	0.38
27	Zone 2 (SMSP)	Cosmoledo and Astove Archipelago Sustainable Use Area	Astove	0.07
28	Marine National Park (Pre-SMSP)	Ile Cocos, Ile La Fouche, Ilot Platte	Coco Island	0.00
29	Marine National Park (Pre-SMSP)	Silhouette Island Marine National Park	Silhouette Island	0.00
30	Special Reserve (Pre-SMSP)	Aride Island Special Nature Reserve	Aride Island	0.00
31	Special Reserve (Pre-SMSP)	Cousin Special Nature Reserve	TBD (no extensive seagrass at Cousin)	0.00
32	Zone 1 (SMSP)	Aldabra Group (Marine) National Park	Other	0.00
33	Zone 3 (SMSP)	Inner Islands Multiple Use Area	TBD, Mahe Plateau Inner Island	
	Zone 3 (SMSP)	Inner Islands Multiple Use Area	Beauvallon Bay, Mahe	
	Zone 3 (SMSP)	Inner Islands Multiple Use Area	Anse La Mouche, Mahe	
	Zone 3 (SMSP)	Inner Islands Multiple Use Area	Grand Anse, Praslin	
	Zone 3 (SMSP)	Inner Islands Multiple Use Area	Consolation, Praslin	

Scenario 3 – Implementation Feasibility and Monitoring Capacity

SMSP Zone/ Type	Region	Location	Responsible
Marine National Park (Pre-SMSP)	Saint Anne Marine National Park	TBD	SPGA
Marine National Park (Pre-SMSP)	Curieuse Marine National Park	Curieuse	SPGA
Marine National Park (Pre-SMSP)	Baie Ternay Marine National Park	Cap Ternay Bay	SPGA
Marine National Park (Pre-SMSP)	Port Launay Marine National Park	Port Launay Bay	SPGA
Marine National Park (Pre-SMSP)	Silhouette Island Marine National Park	Silhouette Island	ICS
Shell Reserve	Mahe (Anse Faure-Fairy Land) Shell Reseve	Anse aux Pins	BERI/ UniSey
Special Reserve (Pre-SMSP)	Aldabra (Marine) Special Reserve	Aldabra	SIF
Zone 1 (SMSP)	D'Arros Atoll (Marine) National Park	D'Arros	SOSF
Zone 2 (SMSP)	Amirantes to Fortune Bank (Marine) Sustainable Use Area	Ile Platte	ICS
Zone 2 (SMSP)	Desroches Atoll (Marine) Sustainable Use Area	Desroches Island	ICS
Zone 2 (SMSP)	Alphonse Group (Marine) Sustainable Use Area	Alphonse, Bijoutier and St Francois	ICS
Zone 2 (SMSP)	Amirantes to Fortune Bank (Marine) Sustainable Use Area	St Joseph	SOSF
Zone 2 (SMSP)	Cosmoledo and Astove Archipelago Sustainable Use Area	Astove	ICS
Zone 2 (SMSP)	Denis Island (Marine) Sustainable Use Area	Denis Island	GIF
Zone 3 (SMSP)	Inner Islands Multiple Use Area	Baie Ste Anne, Praslin	PFA / MECENR
Zone 3 (SMSP)	Inner Islands Multiple Use Area	Cote D'Or, Praslin	MECENR / Management Committee
Zone 3 (SMSP)	Inner Islands Multiple Use Area	Beauvallon Bay, Mahe	MCSS